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Engaging Citizens with Mission Ocean & Waters: A toolbox of approaches

Guidance on methods for facilitating, monitoring and assessing citizen participation levels and for rolling out a European wide network of assemblies of citizens

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Executive Summary

This toolbox supports inclusive and effective citizen engagement in the context of the EU Mission Ocean & Waters. It offers practical tools, strategic guidance, and tested methods for involving people in shaping marine and freshwater research, governance, and innovation. Whether you are designing a local consultation, co-creating a community habitat restoration project, planning a citizens' assembly, or developing a funding application, the toolbox serves as a **navigation aid** — helping you steer engagement efforts from concept to impact.

Citizen engagement is not just about filling a room — it's about **sharing decisions**. When done well it can increase legitimacy, improve outcomes, and foster long-term relationships between communities, policymakers, and the ocean. However, engagement strategies must be tailored to context. This toolbox helps users choose the right approach by linking the *type of engagement* to the *type of problem*, risk level, and desired outcomes.

The content is organised into six parts:

- **Part 1** provides detail on 'how to use this toolbox'.
- **Part 2** introduces tools to help you plan citizen engagement — including tips and templates for selecting participants, ideas for how to engage them effectively, and how to monitor your progress and success. It also offers suggestions for improving funding applications, with a focus on expanding the range of tools used in Mission Ocean & Waters projects.
- **Part 3** presents the same tools, but with added context — offering both the theoretical foundations and practical insights behind how and why they work.
- **Part 4** shares practical examples from EU-funded projects and networks that are working towards the citizen participation goals of The Mission. They demonstrate diverse approaches in real-world settings, that readers may consider adapting, repeating, or connecting with in your own context.
- **Part 5** provide implementation tools; methods for citizen engagement.
- **Part 6** summarizes the toolbox with eight recommendations for citizen engagement with Mission Ocean & Waters.
- **Appendices 1 to 4** provide implementation tools — including more detailed templates, a suite of methodological approaches and tools for consideration.

A core emphasis throughout is on **inclusion and equity**, in line with the *Leave No One Behind* (LNOB) principle. The toolbox encourages users to consider exclusion not only in structural terms (who is missing), but also as a subjective experience (how participation feels) and as a design question (what we can do differently). The toolbox also discusses when inclusion may not be appropriate in the local context, and some of the ethical concerns projects should consider.

The toolbox is designed to support alignment with the Mission's **eight citizen engagement targets** (Appendix 4), and to help build lasting, connected, and trusted forms of participation across Europe's marine and maritime regions.

Glossary and abbreviations

Actors	A ‘social actor’ or simple ‘actor’ is a term used to describe a person (or organisation) who plays a role in the process / problem of interest.
Citizen	Emphasises the non-specialist, non-elite nature of the individuals in question. This creates some distinction from the sometimes-overlapping term stakeholder
Citizens’ assembly (CA)	Many versions of citizens’ assemblies exist, but it could generally be described as a body of randomly selected citizens that deliberate, and in some cases vote, on one or several issues that have implications at the citizen level.
Citizen Engagement	Refers to a broad set of activities involving people in public processes related to Mission Ocean & Waters.
Citizen Science	Promotes collaboration between non-professionals and scientists in a two-way process. Citizens can engage from co-design through data collection to result interpretation. Scientists gain capacity; citizens gain knowledge and recognition. ¹
Community	Refers to geographically or socially linked groups of citizens, used in place-based contexts.
Community of Practice (CoP)	A group of people who share a concern or passion about a topic and deepen their knowledge by interacting regularly. Activities include mutual learning, co-creation, and best practice exchange. Less structured than a network and may reflect more diverse perspectives. ²
Controllable problem	A problem with uncertainty that can be reduced / minimized, and where agreement and consensus on norms and decisions are achievable. Any uncertainty can usually be described through objective and quantifiable measures. Here, normal scientific risk analysis can be sufficient, for example, forecasting for waves and levels of toxins in mussels.
Uncontrollable problem	A problem with uncertainty that cannot be predicted or controlled, there are significant knowledge gaps, and a situation where there is often no consensus and little agreement on norms, standards or the likely decisions that need to be made. Simple probabilistic risk analysis or standard statistical methods are not able to fill all the knowledge gaps. For example, climate change impacts such as sea level rise and associated consequences including coastal erosion.
Deliberative turn	A renewed concern with the authenticity of democracy – the degree to which democratic control is substantive rather than symbolic and engaged by competent citizens. ³
Ladder of Participation	The principles of participation are typically illustrated as a ladder which describe a spectrum of engagement depths, and their corresponding levels of citizen power related to a decision that needs to be made (Figure 2 Citizen participation spectrum, page 14). In the ladder, increasing levels of engagement

¹ Garcia-Soto et al. (2021)

² Wenger et al. (2002); Vetter (2020)

³ Dryzek (2002)

means greater citizen power. At the top of the ladder, citizens have the power to define the problem, develop the solution and the process to get there.⁴

Leave No One Behind (LNOB)	A foundational value of the UN SDGs, requiring that discrimination and inequality be addressed. Ensures appropriate opportunities for all to participate. ⁵
Mission Ocean & Waters ('the Mission')	European Union Commission's Mission: Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030 . The Mission aims to, within the target of 2030, protect and restore the health of our ocean and waters through research and innovation, citizen engagement and blue investments. ⁶
Network	A named group of entities concerned with a topic. Networks persist over time, even as members change. They connect individuals, institutions, and projects with shared objectives.
Participation	Participation may entail a range of involvement, for example, from differing levels of communication (i.e., receiving information or voicing opinions), to directly impacting how we need to consider the risks involved, both for those participating and for the project's outcomes a research process unfolds or what the outcomes are. While the avenues for participation vary in function and intensity, it is a widespread agreement that participation should grant a greater degree of power to citizens.
Post-normal science	Applies in situations where facts are uncertain, values are in dispute, stakes are high, and decisions are urgent. Public participation is essential for solving such problems and ensuring processes are credible and legitimate
Stakeholder	Organised interests such as NGOs, businesses, or authorities. Distinct from citizens unless otherwise noted.
Steps of participation	A tool we provide to you to help you to visualise the 'steps of participation' and assess when it is most appropriate to inform, consult or empower citizens (see Figure 3).
Wicked problem	Issues that are difficult to solve with scientific evidence or knowledge alone, due to the many interconnected, interdependent social problems that make finding a single solution impossible. ⁷

⁴ Arnstein (1969)

⁵ UN Sustainable Development Goals: <https://unsdg.un.org/2030-agenda/universal-values/leave-no-one-behind>

⁶ [EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters](#)

⁷ Rittel & Webber (1973)

1 Part 1: Welcome to the PREP4BLUE toolbox for engaging citizens in your project

1.1 What is this toolbox?

Public mobilisation and engagement are crucial elements in the European Commission’s **EU Mission: Restore Our Ocean & Waters** (referred in this document also as ‘Mission Ocean & Waters’ or ‘the Mission’). Not quite sure what Mission Ocean & Waters is all about? You are in the right place! With a 2030 target, the Mission aims to protect and restore the health of our ocean and waters through research and innovation, citizen engagement and blue investments⁸. You can find plenty more information on the Mission, and how it might apply to you, throughout this guide.

This toolbox supports effective **citizen engagement** in Mission Ocean & Waters — in other words, how to meaningfully involve people in in shaping, contributing to, and influencing marine-related decisions, actions, and knowledge. Also known as public participation, civic involvement, or citizen participation, we use both ‘citizen engagement’ and ‘citizen participation’ as umbrella terms throughout this toolbox.

What we can tell you now is that there is a wealth of approaches that facilitate engagement with The Mission, whether through co-production of knowledge, citizen participation, activation and training, hackathons, citizen science initiatives and others.

Among this variety, it can be challenging to acquire an overview of what you need to do with whom to achieve your goal. In this document, we offer a toolbox that introduces project organisers to The Mission, explores different types of citizen engagement, risks associated with citizen engagement, who to engage and how to do this successfully, how to evaluate your success, together with a deeper dive into the science behind our suggestions.

1.2 Who is the toolbox aimed at?

Simply put, this toolbox provides a framework to guide users, no matter what their experience, to support citizen engagement with Mission Ocean & Waters. However, the toolbox can be used to develop any project involving people – from individual members of the public to targeted organisations, sectors or even researchers and politicians. Therefore, this toolbox can apply to any of the following:

- A. Practitioners:** Anyone (individual, organisation, institution, initiative) working on citizen engagement in marine and freshwater matters across Europe.
- B. Project consortia:** Individuals and organisations applying for, or successful in gaining, funding under future EU Oceans Pact / Mission Restore our Ocean & Water calls.
- C. Researchers and Innovators:** This guide sets a foundation for further research into participatory methods, direct democracy and bottom-up governance for marine and freshwater matters.

⁸ [EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters](#)

- D. The European Commission:** This guide will be delivered to the European Commission and, where appropriate, will hopefully influence the shape of future funding calls in line with the best practices outlined herein.

1.3 How to use this toolbox

To reflect different people's needs, we have split the toolbox into five parts, and you will be asked prompting questions throughout the guide to take you where you need to go.

Each part supports a different stage of your citizen engagement work: from planning and recruiting to choosing methods and evaluating impact. Whether you're working on a small local consultation or a multi-country Mission Ocean & Waters initiative, you can select the parts most relevant to your project.

The structure follows a simple logic:

- **Part 1** provides details on how to use this toolbox.
- **Part 2** introduces tools to help you plan citizen engagement — including tips and templates for selecting participants, ideas for how to engage them effectively, and how to monitor your progress and success. It also offers suggestions for improving funding applications, with a focus on expanding the range of tools used in Mission Ocean & Waters projects.
- **Part 3** presents the same tools, but with added context — offering both the theoretical foundations and practical insights behind how and why they work.
- **Part 4** shares practical examples from EU-funded projects and networks that are working towards the citizen participation goals of The Mission. This part includes examples of many of the tools presented in the previous Parts 2 and 3 of the guide. They demonstrate diverse approaches in real-world settings, that readers may consider adapting, repeating, or connecting with, in your own context.
- **Part 5** is a toolbox of specific methods that can be used to help with citizen engagement; survey, citizen's assemblies, future scenario workshops, semi-structured interviews, walking interviews, participatory mapping and strategic ocean literacy as a way of working.
- **Part 6** summarizes the toolbox with eight recommendations for citizen engagement with Mission Ocean & Waters.
- **Appendices 1 to 4** provide implementation tools — including more detailed templates and evaluation tools for consideration.

Parts 2 and 3 offer tools and background depending on how much detail you need, under the following subheadings:

- Introduction to engaging citizens with Mission Ocean & Waters
- Types of participation to consider, depending on risk and desired outcome (Part 3 only)
- Who should you engage? Tools for planning engagement
- How should you involve citizens? Tools for planning for implementation
- And why are you doing it again? Tools planning for impact – monitoring and evaluating citizen engagement

Practical tips, examples, and shortcuts are highlighted throughout. Use what you need — and adapt as you go.

Now, let's dive right in and test it out!

Please select which of the following parts describes you best and we will take you where you need to go (click on the titles):

- **Part 2:** *I work on small projects, may have my own processes or have done a lot of citizen engagement, so I am less interested in the science behind citizen engagement.*
- **Part 3:** *I am building a new project and want to start from scratch to engage a diversity of citizens and stakeholders, or I would like to dive deeper into the science behind citizen engagement.*²⁶
- **Part 4:** *I just want to see some examples of the ways that projects can engage with Mission Ocean & Waters.*

This toolbox is also available at: [Engaging Citizens with Mission Ocean and Waters](#)

2 Part 2: A practitioner's toolbox: I work on small projects, may have my own processes or have done a lot of citizen engagement, so I am less interested in the science behind citizen engagement

HIGHLIGHTS

- Engaging with Mission Ocean & Waters can help secure funding, and engaging citizens in The Mission can help provide new knowledge AND empower the people involved to solve their local problems.
- However, people new to citizen engagement should ensure they have the appropriate knowledge to undertake effective participation. This guide can help you!
- Citizen participation is not necessary for all type of problems, and precautions should be taken for when, why and how to engage them.
- The steps of citizen engagement, from informing to empowering (Figure 3), are presented as a tool to understand when citizen participation is needed and not, and which level of participation is appropriate.
- This toolbox provides tools to guide you through your project planning including: Guiding questions to consider before planning and stakeholder mapping templates (Table 1, Table 2) and help towards strategic planning and evaluating your impact (Table 3, Table 4).
- More detailed background and advice is available in Part 3 of this toolbox.
- A range of citizen engagement tools is provided in Part 5 of the toolbox.

2.1 Introduction to engaging citizens with Mission Ocean & Waters

Modelled on the Apollo 11 Mission that landed people on the Moon, the European Union (EU) created five Missions (Cancer, Soil, Climate, Smart Cities, and Ocean) to tackle global challenges, with the help of society. Missions are about transitioning from sector-based to problem-based policymaking, mobilizing resources and citizens in the service of bold objectives that address the so-called *wicked problems* of our time⁹.

Wicked problems are issues that are difficult to solve with scientific evidence or knowledge alone, due to the many interconnected, interdependent social problems that make finding a single solution impossible¹⁰. Problems like climate change, biodiversity loss, and food insecurity are good examples. Addressing this type of problem and advancing the Mission involves engaging a wider range of social actors, especially civil society. A *social actor*, or simply an 'actor', is a term used to describe a person (or organisation) who plays a role in the process / problem of interest. Climate change, biodiversity loss and food insecurity are typical examples of wicked problems that are global in scope, have contested understandings, and require collective action, from individuals to policy level.

The starting point for this toolbox is how to help projects advance Mission Ocean & Waters through strategic engagement with citizens and partners. The framing of the problem is already defined: The

⁹ Mazzucato (2021)

¹⁰ Rittel & Webber (1973)

Mission has given its overarching goal (Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030, or restoration), to be achieved through three specific Mission Objectives, applied across four pre-defined European sea/river basins ('Lighthouses') (see Figure 1 below). The Mission's objectives must be translated into relevant and actionable tasks that engage and motivate people. The Mission has outlined a list of eight specific target outcomes relating specifically to citizen engagement with Mission Ocean & Waters (listed in Appendix 4102), that may be useful to consider when mapping how your project could be planned around the Mission ambitions.

FIGURE 1. OVERVIEW OF THE PRIMARY MISSION OCEAN & WATERS OBJECTIVES IN EACH RIVER AND SEA BASINS UPON THE MISSION'S LAUNCH IN 2021.

2.1.1 Why engage with the Mission?

If you're applying for funding under the Mission, it's important to align your project with its three main objectives and target outcomes. This toolbox is designed to help you do just that. Ideally, you should define how your project supports these goals before you apply – that way, you're more likely to secure the right resources to succeed. And more importantly, with a strategic approach from the start, we can collectively work towards solving one of the EU's biggest wicked problems: *Restoring our Ocean and Waters before 2030*.

2.1.2 Why engage with citizens?

From the very beginning, the EU Missions have been designed with the underlying principle that their success will depend on the participation of citizens, appropriate to the issue at hand.^{11,12} To increase citizen knowledge, understanding of, and care for Mission Ocean & Waters objectives (or challenges), especially with local framing, can lead to bottom-up initiatives in line with the Mission. A collaborative approach to understanding and care from your project could lead to empowerment of communities

¹¹ Mazzucato (2018)

¹² Mazzucato (2019)

to help restore their ocean and waters across different sectors and scales, from individual to policy level.

In general, when used in this toolbox, **'citizen'** emphasises the non-specialist, non-elite nature of the individuals in question¹³. This creates some distinction from the sometimes-overlapping term stakeholder (also often used throughout the Mission literature). **Stakeholders**, by contrast, may be either specialist, elite, have access to the Mission activities due to their employment, or some other form of contextual privilege. They also tend to be represented as organisations or interest groups, while citizens tend to be engaged as individuals. That said, the two concepts often overlap and, of course, individual stakeholders can also be citizens, and citizens may be stakeholders. And the tools provided in this toolbox can be applied to either or both.

The ultimate goal of this toolbox is to provide guidance that supports the citizen participation goals of Mission Ocean & Waters.

If you would like more details on the Mission, the theoretical grounding of this toolbox or more detail on tools, please see Part 3 of the toolbox.

2.2 Types of engagement to consider: Steps of participation engagement from informing, to empowering

Before planning any project, leaders like you must ask some key questions to ensure that your goals are achievable. In the case of engaging citizens in the Mission, we should first ask:

- When should we be targeting different citizens and / or stakeholders?
- Why are we asking them for their participation?
- What are the risks involved? both for those participating and for the project's outcomes?
- Importantly, given the type of problem we're addressing or the kind of participation we're asking for: How likely is success?

Participation may entail a range of involvement, for example, from differing levels of communication (receiving information or voicing opinions) to directly impacting how we need to consider the risks involved, both for those participating and for the project's outcomes a research process unfolds or what the outcomes are. While the avenues for participation vary in function and intensity, it is a widespread agreement that participation should grant a greater degree of power to citizens. The principles of participation are typically illustrated as a ladder¹⁴ which describe a spectrum of engagement depths and their corresponding levels of citizen power related to a decision that needs to be made (Figure 2 below). In the ladder, increasing levels of engagement means greater citizen power. At the top of the ladder, citizens have the power to define the problem, develop the solution and the process to get there. Note that we illustrate the ladder as a matrix (Figure 2).

This matrix, or the ladder of participation, can be used to 'diagnose' the level of engagement required for different participatory processes. While there may be good reasons to include citizen, it is important to underline that not all problems require the greatest levels of involvement – this depends

¹³ Chwalisz (2020)

¹⁴ Arnstein (1969)

on the type of problem at hand. If you would like more detail on types of problems and risks, see Part 3.

		DEGREE OF CITIZEN DECISION-MAKING POWER				
		INFORM	CONSULT	INVOLVE	COLLABORATE	EMPOWER
PARTICIPATION GOAL		To provide the public with balanced and objective information to assist them in understanding the problem, alternatives, opportunities and/or solutions.	To obtain public feedback on analysis, alternatives and/or decisions.	To work directly with citizens throughout the process to ensure that public concerns and aspirations are consistently understood and considered.	To partner with citizens in each aspect of the decision, including the development of alternatives and the identification of the preferred solutions or activities.	To place final decision-making in the hands of citizens.
	PROMISE TO THE PUBLIC	The Mission initiative will keep citizens informed.	The Mission initiative will keep citizens informed, listen to and acknowledge concerns and aspirations, and provide feedback on how public input influenced the decision.	The Mission initiative will work with citizens to ensure that their concerns and aspirations are directly reflected in the alternatives developed and provide feedback on how public input influenced the decision.	The Mission initiative will look to citizens for advice and innovation in formulating solutions and incorporate advice and recommendations into the decisions to the maximum extent possible.	The Mission initiative will implement what citizens decide and/or co-implement and co-lead initiative.

FIGURE 2. CITIZEN PARTICIPATION SPECTRUM, FROM INFORMING TO EMPOWERING. ADAPTED FROM IAP2 INTERNATIONAL FEDERATION (2014).

A diagnostic tool is provided in Figure 3 below to help you visualise the ‘steps of participation’ and assess when it is most appropriate to inform, consult or empower citizens. Overall, engaging citizens in the Mission aims to empower them to take responsibility and action for the ultimate goal: To restore our ocean and waters. However, the Mission is a complex, uncontrollable problem with ambiguous scope of risk; but which step does your project goal sit on these continuum, and what type of participation should you be aiming for?

FIGURE 3. DIAGNOSTIC TOOL: VISUALISING THE **STEPS OF PARTICIPANT ENGAGEMENT** FROM INFORMING TO EMPOWERING, ACCORDING TO SCOPE OF RISKS AND EXPECTATIONS WITHIN PROJECTS. DEVELOPED FOR PREP4BLUE.

Reflecting on what we have learned about the ladder of participation, and the steps to empowerment, (Figure 2 and Figure 3), we can identify that traditionally many scientific projects may have tackled controlled, low risk problems, and then informed citizens about the knowledge they have revealed, in a one-way attempt to keep scientists **informed**. However, more and more transdisciplinary projects aim to solve more uncontrollable problems, with uncertain risks, by **consulting, involving and/or collaborating** with specific experts and knowledge holders, for instance in participatory science for fisheries management. As citizen science’s potential has peaked the interests of governments and scientists alike, as a way of both collecting information and involving society with more uncontrollable and ambiguous problems, we have the potential to **empower citizens in their decision-making** potential, if done well.

Part 4 provides specific examples of different types of citizen engagement working towards Mission Ocean & Waters, where projects may utilise different ‘steps’ across the ladder for different aspects of their project, depending on the type of inputs and level of engagement required.

2.2.1 Who? Tools for planning engagement

Careful planning of participatory processes is crucial—not only to prevent presumptions about citizen involvement or the risk of participant ‘burnout’, but also to protect the success of this project and pave the way for future initiatives. The preceding section introduced the idea there are many reasons to include different actors (citizens or stakeholders) in your project. Maybe different people will be involved at different stages, or maybe you require the same people throughout. This section can help guide you through a careful thought process to establish who you really need to engage with, and why.

In reality, multiple challenges often arise with participatory approaches, including who to include in which part of the process, how to include them, and are they interested in participating at all? This is often referred to as **stakeholder or engagement fatigue** in participatory processes. Reasons for this type of fatigue varies, but is typically related to time constraints, language barriers, different priorities

(such as other things happening locally pressing on their time), poor personal reward (where they cannot see any self-gain) or perceptions that they have little capacity/power to influence decisions.¹⁵

2.2.2 Questions to ask your project during planning stages

To minimise risks of stakeholder fatigue, and maximise chances of success, careful planning is required before you engage any citizens. You may already have ample experience engaging citizens; you may have a bank of existing willing participants, or a process that has been developed over 30 years of practise. In the last 30 years and driven by initiatives such as Mission Ocean & Waters, many funders (and therefore many funded organisations) have moved from informing citizens to trying to empower them through participatory processes. As project planners, we must ensure that we consider factors to minimise stakeholder fatigue, broaden our participant base, maximise the gain the participants get from involvement, lift our gaze from our own projects to also ensure that we deliver our promises to the public and a positive legacy for future citizen engagement.

Table 1 below provides a useful set of guiding questions for any project to help ensure that a clear understanding of itself from the start, and who should be invited to participate.

TABLE 1. GUIDING REFLECTION QUESTIONS FOR PREPARING FOR CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT ¹⁶

	Guiding questions/suggestions	Comments
Framing your project	What is the focus area of the project?	For instance, coastal zone planning or waste disposal?
	What type of problem are you dealing with?	Controllable / Uncontrollable (See Part 3, Section 3.1.1 if you are uncertain)
	What is the scope of risk?	Simple/complex/ uncertain/ambiguous (see Section 3.1.3 and Figure 3).
	What do you hope to obtain by including citizens in your project?	Define your goals, objectives and expected results, for different parts within your project. (see participation goals in Figure 2)
Planning who should participate	Map your participants to define the different relevant actors you need to provide different types of input, at different levels of participation.	See Figure 3 (page 14) and use the participant mapping template below (Table 2) to guide this.
	Consider the <i>Leave No One Behind</i> principles	After mapping your participants, consider who might be left behind? Why? And is it appropriate to try to overcome these barriers of engagement? If so, how?
	If activities have a high level of complexity in terms of engagement, you may divide them into sub-problems with corresponding sub-activities	This will allow stakeholder identification and engagement at sub-activity level.

¹⁵ See Jönsson & Swartling (2014)

¹⁶ Source: Questions adapted from Zimmermann and Maennling (2007), and Durham E., Baker H., Smith M., Moore E. & Morgan V. (2014). The BiodivERSA Stakeholder Engagement Handbook. BiodivERSA, Paris (108 pp).

	Place activities in a timeline. Do some activities depend on the implementation of other activities?	At what stage should citizens be engaged in my project? Consider barriers, including stakeholder fatigue and external demands on their time.
Pre-planning for evaluation What is your desired impact?	Consider methods carefully	Are the methods selected appropriate? (see Part 5).
	How will you know if planned engagement and methods are working well?	Think about essential metrics early – will you evaluate this qualitatively or quantitatively?
	What is the desired impact of the engagement process on project results?	How will you evaluate this? You can use different types of tools to gather this information e.g., e-mail, survey or workshop.
	What is the desired impact of engagement for participants?	How will you evaluate this? You can use different types of tools to gather this information e.g., e-mail, survey or workshop.
	How can you learn through the project, review and adapt methods / approaches / participants?	How?

2.2.3 Mapping your participant needs

Mapping participants is important to get an overview of who you aim to include, and who you actually manage to include (see Table 2 below). Given the principle of *Leave No One Behind* (LNOB), effort should be taken to ensure gender and equality issues are reflected upon. For instance, if target participants are alone with small children, it can be difficult to participate in meetings during the afternoon; and if others don't have a car, they may not travel far, and there may be identity/religious/historical reasons for avoiding buildings such as churches. It is also important to consider the ethics of their inclusion, whether it is appropriate to ask for their time and whether your method of inclusion or dissemination may fuel local conflict, which could risk the success of the project or reputation of your problem.

A more detailed stakeholder mapping template, which considers power and legitimacy more thoroughly, is available in Executive Summary

TABLE 2. PARTICIPANT MAPPING TEMPLATE. BASED ON SOURCE: EMPOWERUS PROJECT: [HTTPS://EMPOWERUS-PROJECT.EU/](https://empowerus-project.eu/)

Participant type	Name	Organization, network or interest group	Contact details (e-mail)	Brief summary of their stake or agenda	Motivation to participate	Type of input required (knowledge / experience & reflections / co-production and responsibility)	Level of participation (inform, consult, involve, collaborate or empower)	Where in project do you need participation?	When?	Barriers to participation?	Ethical considerations	Engagement types / method?
Intergovernmental												
Public National												
Public Regional												
Public Local government												
Sub-local												
Private sector												
Non-local NGO												
Citizen												
Who might be left behind?												

2.3 How? Tools for planning for implementation

This section covers a range of different citizen engagement tools with explanations of the step-by-step process of implementing them (preparation, during and after). Many of the methods may apply to both stakeholder and citizen engagement, as these terms often overlap. According to your Mission Ocean & Waters initiative and the problem you are to solve, some tools are more appropriate than others, and this toolbox is not exhaustive. Therefore, we recommend reflecting on the guiding questions in Table 1 before deciding on your chosen method. We also suggest exploring the wide range of stakeholder engagement methods guides that are available online^{17,18}.

When implementing a method that involves several citizens or groups, it is important to consider the power relations between organizer/researcher and participants, and between participants (see detailed stakeholder mapping in Appendix 1: Additional planning templates to guide project planning). When inviting citizens to participate, think about the location that you choose for your activity. Aim for a place where participants feel comfortable. For each tool, it is encouraged to revisit your reflection on the *Leave No One Behind* principle and aim for inclusion and diversity in your informants¹⁹.

Methods for citizen engagement included in this toolbox (see Part 5 and the following referred sections):

- 5.1 Survey
- 5.2 Citizen's assemblies
- 5.3 Future scenario workshop
- 5.4 Semi-structured interviews
- 5.5 Walking interviews
- 5.6 Participatory mapping
- 5.7 Strategic ocean literacy as a way of working

In developing an engagement strategy, several key questions need to be addressed. Table 3 below may also guide you in choosing an appropriate tool for type of problem you are dealing with, and the level of participation you are aiming for. Table 3 should be used in conjunction with the guiding questions and participant mapping given in Table 1 and Table 2.

The participation level in Table 3 below depends on how your project decides to involve the citizens in the process and the level of decision-making power delegated to them, and the tools you choose to engage citizens to incorporate their input needs to reflect these points. For instance, if you decide to implement a citizens' assembly, you may also delegate decision-making power in the form of voting, to the participants (Empower).

¹⁷ <http://actioncatalogue.eu/search>

¹⁸ <http://gap2.eu/methodological-toolbox/>

¹⁹ United Nation on 'Leave No One Behind': <https://tinyurl.com/bdf4rc8s>

TABLE 3. PARTICIPATION LEVEL DECISION MAKING MATRIX

Problem type/participation level	Controllable problem	Uncontrollable problem
Inform	Newsletters, flyers, campaigns, websites, social media etc. (traditional ocean literacy)	
Consult	Survey , Citizens' Assemblies	Future scenarios , Semi-structured interviews , Walking interviews , Participatory mapping
Involve	Citizens' Assemblies, Ocean literacy	Future scenarios , Participatory mapping
Collaborate	Ocean literacy	Citizens' Assemblies , Future scenarios , Participatory mapping , Ocean literacy
Empower	Ocean literacy	Citizens' Assemblies , Future scenarios , Ocean literacy

2.4 Why? Tools for planning impact – monitoring and evaluating citizen engagement

Ideally, before inception or very early on in your project, you have considered the guiding questions provided in Table 1. Recall that as different Mission Ocean & Waters initiatives will aim to solve a variety of problems, they will all require different levels of participation and will relate to different contexts. Using the same tables before, during and after project start can be useful to reflect on your aims, and to better be able to evaluate whether those aims are met during and after the project start. Constant reflection and adaptation are a key to success in co-created projects. Co-creation refers to the collaborative process where diverse actors—such as citizens, scientists, practitioners and policymakers—jointly shape goals, methods and solutions, recognising each other's knowledge and experiences as valuable throughout the project lifecycle. So regularly revisit the answers you gave in Table 1 and Table 2, in conjunction with Table 4 below to plan your re-iterative evaluation strategy below.

TABLE 4. CITIZEN/STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT EVALUATION TABLE. A CITIZEN/STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT EVALUATION TABLE THAT IS USEFUL AT THE OUTSET TO PLAN A STRATEGY FOR A PROJECT/INITIATIVE.

	What do you want to know?	What evaluation methods will you use?	How will the evaluation be conducted?
Planning process			
Engagement			
Benefits/outcomes			

2.5 Evaluation in relation to Mission Ocean & Waters

It is useful to note that funders often require funded projects to provide a high level, summative evaluation of their approach and impact on wider society that specifically focus on aspects of their funding criteria. As we focus here on supporting the goals of Mission Ocean & Waters, Appendix 1: Additional planning templates to guide project planning and Appendix 2: Additional tools to help planning evaluation and monitoring provides a useful tool for planning and mapping your subsequent impact at high level on The Mission target outcomes, objectives and overarching goal. This simplified way of mapping can be adapted for any project goal, at any level.

If you are interested in more specific evaluation of your impact towards Mission Ocean & Waters, more evaluation tables are available in Part 3.

2.5.1 Evaluating impact on societal ocean literacy

Increasingly, funding calls related to the Mission ask for ocean literacy to be embedded in the project. Ocean literacy refers to the understanding of the ocean's influence on us—and our influence on the ocean—and encompasses not just knowledge, but also attitudes, behaviours and a sense of responsibility. As a result, Appendix 2 provides a simple planning template through which you can plan the goals and anticipated outcomes of your ocean literacy activities and prompts to help you start thinking about the best methods of evaluation. Figure 4 below gives an example of how this can be used to inspire planning your activities around the known dimensions of ocean literacy (presented as a method in Appendix 4) and suggestions of ways to start more detailed formative evaluation.

FIGURE 4. MAPPING THE AIMS AND IMPACT OF OCEAN LITERACY WITHIN A PROJECT. AN EXAMPLE OF WORKING WITH WATER QUALITY ACROSS STAKEHOLDER GROUPS²⁰

²⁰ Based on the 7 Essential Principles of Ocean Science (NMEA, 2024), and 10 currently accepted dimensions known to impact ocean literacy (McKinley et al. 2023).

3 Part 3: Big project and researcher's guide: I am building a new project and want to start from scratch to engage a diversity of citizens and stakeholders

HIGHLIGHTS

- We provide a theoretical and scientific background to assist in your funding applications for projects related to Mission Ocean & Waters.
- Citizen participation is not necessary for all types of problems, and precautions should be taken for when, why and how to engage them.
- Knowledge and interest among citizens about Mission Ocean & Waters must be created through processes that are perceived as credible, salient and legitimate to be translated into action.
- The steps of citizen engagement, from informing to empowering, are presented as a tool to understand when citizen participation is needed and not, and which level of participation is appropriate.
- Based on the above, we provide tools to guide you through your project planning, including: guiding questions to consider before planning and stakeholder mapping templates (see Table 7 and Table 8), a range of citizen engagement tools (Table 9) and help towards strategic planning and evaluating your impact (Table 10, Table 11, and Table 12).

3.1 Introduction to engaging citizens with Mission Ocean & Waters

The five EU Missions — *Cancer, Soil, Climate, Smart Cities, and Ocean & Waters* — are designed to be ambitious and inspiring. They aim to tackle complex societal challenges using a whole-of-society approach, requiring collaboration across disciplines, sectors, and communities. Rather than being sector-specific, these Missions take a problem-oriented approach, mobilizing both resources and people to address the wicked problems of our time²¹. Wicked problems are complex, dynamic challenges that are difficult to define clearly, have no single solution, and where actions taken often generate unforeseen consequences. For Mission Ocean & Waters, the collective goal is clear: **Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030**. This Mission opens the door to **diverse funding opportunities**—not just for conventional ocean science, but for projects of all types and scales that can contribute to this goal. Solutions must be broad, inclusive, and grounded in real-world action.

Wicked problems are such that scientific evidence, or knowledge, alone is not enough to answer them. Problems like climate change, biodiversity loss, and food insecurity are good examples. These issues are global, complex, and often contested—requiring **collective action and broader societal involvement**. As a result, the way to go about addressing these types of problems and advancing the Missions involves engaging a wider range of social actors, especially of civil society.

This toolbox is not about redefining the Mission; it's about helping your project contribute to it effectively. The problem has already been framed: Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030, via three overarching objectives, applied across four regional *Lighthouses* (European sea and river basins), see Figure 5 below.

²¹ Mazzucato (2021)²² Cash & Belloy (2020)

FIGURE 5. OVERVIEW OF THE PRIMARY MISSION OCEAN & WATERS OBJECTIVES IN EACH RIVER AND SEA BASINS AT THE LAUNCH OF THE MISSION IN 2021.

The transformation that is needed to achieve the Mission will affect people’s lives both directly and indirectly. Therefore, success hinges on active engagement, not passive acceptance. People must become agents of change, not just recipients of policy. To be meaningful, the Mission’s goals must be: a) known and understood; b) supported at all levels (EU, national, regional, and local), and c) seen as credible, relevant and legitimate.

This approach involves broadening how challenges and solutions are defined — by including diverse forms of knowledge beyond academic science and working closely with local actors. One example is when local authorities use data from coastal citizen science groups as part of ongoing environmental monitoring. In support of this, the Mission sets out eight specific citizen engagement targets, which are listed in Appendix 4.

The objective your project focuses on might not be the most pressing for every community in a given region. Claiming that your goal is ‘the most important’ across a large sea or river basin can hinder citizen engagement — especially among national or international stakeholders/policy makers— and potentially weaken your funding prospects.

So, when using this toolbox, tailor your approach to the local context, and be clear about your focus before applying for funding. This will help ensure you’re asking for the right resources to meet your goals.

By increasing local knowledge, understanding, and concern around the Mission’s objectives, your project can spark **bottom-up initiatives** that support the broader goals. A collaborative approach — grounded in local relevance— can empower communities across scales, from individuals to policymakers^{22,23}. To achieve this, consider **localizing top-down objectives** to enhance relevance; **transferring power and ownership** to communities; and designing **participatory processes** linked to real institutions or decision-making bodies. So, in project design we must consider why, who, when and how to engage these different participants.

²² Cash & Belloy (2020)

²³ Bennett et al. (2021)

This toolbox is here to **support your project's citizen engagement strategy** in line with Mission Ocean & Waters. It offers practical guidance to help you navigate participation goals effectively—so that together, we can restore our ocean and waters by 2030. This is illustrated below in Table 5.

TABLE 5. EXPECTED OUTCOMES BY 2025 (1ST PHASE) AND BY 2030 (2ND PHASE) OF MISSION OCEAN & WATERS WITH RESPECT TO CITIZEN PARTICIPATION.²⁴

Expected outcomes by 2025	Tried and applied deliberative democracy mechanisms and social innovation practices for the co-design and co-implementation of solutions for the restoration of the aquatic environment.
	Developed and piloted frameworks and processes for participatory governance and deliberative democracy, including an EU-wide network of assemblies to enable effective citizen and stakeholder involvement in the lighthouses.
	Up-scaled the European Research Area funded pilot citizen science campaign 'Plastic Pirates – Go Europe' together with further Member States.
	Involved the European solidarity corps in restoration projects.
	Promoted apps allowing citizens to collect data and observations and will promote (digital) data collection and participatory research involving citizens for the monitoring and restoration of ocean and waters; the collected data will be harmonised and made publicly available through the Digital Twin Ocean, EMODnet and/or the Copernicus Marine Service.
	Provided knowledge and methodological frameworks to support the revision of the International Ocean Governance agenda.
Expected outcomes by 2030	All European citizens have the opportunity to engage in the preservation and restoration of oceans and waters through participative means, volunteering and citizen science.
	All European citizens are empowered to be actors in the preservation and restoration of oceans and waters through social innovation, awareness raising, education and training.
	Promoted EU-wide annual ocean literacy campaigns, in cooperation with the EU4Ocean Coalition to strengthen public awareness and overcome the emotional disconnect with the ocean and waters.
	Launched regular citizen science campaigns as a part of novel participatory research initiatives to increase the reach, quality and impact of scientific initiatives and boost the environmental awareness of the participants.

3.1.1 Why engage with the Mission? The theory and terminology behind post-normal science

Utilising a theoretical grounding to engage citizens with Mission Ocean & Waters will help in your application for funding and maximise the success of your project going forward. The Mission aims to tackle uncontrollable and wicked problems at societal level across Europe, and with it comes a range of challenges and risks associated with engaging citizens.

This toolbox, and specifically the detail provided in this part of toolbox, is based on a theoretical approach called '*post-normal science*' and has been developed by the PREP4BLUE project team, drawing on their expertise as well as insights from earlier participatory projects, literature and handbooks. Below, we briefly introduce what *post-normal science* means, along with some key terms. This will help explain why citizen participation is central to the Mission Ocean & Waters agenda and how you can apply it in practice.

In the traditional view, knowledge is synonymous with research or science. Since science is often perceived as objective and autonomous from politics, scientific experts are useful for legitimizing

²⁴ Source: European Commission. Implementation Plan for Mission Ocean & Waters.

advice and action – for instance in relation to achieving the objectives of Mission Ocean & Waters²⁵. This is based on the belief that a strict and formal separation between science and society is both possible and necessary²⁶. In this view, science must be ‘pure’ and autonomous to function as an objective source of advice on controversial issues. As such, engaging citizens can be problematic, as this would allow different agendas to influence ‘pure science’. Accordingly, it is necessary to look for other theoretical foundations as the Mission is aiming to including citizens to solve challenges. The theoretical foundation of this toolbox is loosely based on the theory of post-normal science.

The insight of post-normal science goes beyond the traditional idea that science is both certain and value-free²⁷. Post-normal science represent a form of science for policy that address issues where facts are uncertain, values in dispute, stakes high and decisions urgent.²⁸ This philosophy of so-called post-normal science states that for conflict-ridden and complex societal challenges where scientific knowledge is uncertain, democratic approaches are needed to assess what knowledge is relevant, and who manages the validity and relevance of this knowledge (Table 6). This resonates with the challenges that the Mission aims to tackle, including climate change and environmental pollution: what to do, and how to cope with multiple opinions and uncertainties while being under pressure by the public, market forces and political goals?

TABLE 6. POST-NORMAL SCIENCE: KEY CONCEPTS FOR CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT

Focus on:	Approach using:
Solving real-world problems	Issue-driven inquiry
Acknowledging uncertainty	Extended peer communities
Building mutual trust	Participatory processes

Post-normal science acknowledges that uncertainty is more than a technical number or a methodological issue. There are of course several ways to distinguish between different types of uncertainty²⁹, including **uncertainty that can be controlled** through quantification and **uncertainty that cannot be controlled** because these specific problems are sufficiently complex and involve so many competing interests that ‘more’ knowledge will not necessarily reduce the uncertainty in the problem. Uncertainty that cannot be controlled makes the premises for risk analysis unclear and can thus be an additional source of conflict. This may be relevant when the uncertainty cannot be sufficiently reduced with new knowledge. Note that even quantifiable uncertainty can be a subject of conflict. For example, decisions based on quantifiable risk can be fraught with conflict because interest groups can have different preferences for which risk one is willing to take.

The way uncertainty is related to two types of problems is central to this toolbox, and is defined as follows:

- A) Controllable problem:** reducible uncertainty where agreement and consensus on norms are settled. The uncertainty at hand can be described through quantitative measures. Here,

²⁵ Jasanoff et al. (1995)

²⁶ Gieryn (1983)

²⁷ Ravetz (1999)

²⁸ Funtowicz & Ravetz (1993)

²⁹ Funtowicz & Ravetz (1993); Strand & Oughton (2009)

normal scientific risk analysis can be sufficient, for example, forecasting for waves and levels of toxins in mussels. See Appendix 3 for a more detailed example.

- B) Uncontrollable problem:** irreducible uncertainty with no consensus and little agreement on norms and standards. Context where simple probabilistic risk analysis or standard statistical methods are not able to fill all knowledge gaps, and we lack knowledge about what we do not know, for example, climate change impacts such as sea level rise and associated consequences including coastal erosion. See Appendix 3 for a more detailed example.

The Mission aims to solve a large number of complex problems that have different types of uncertainties related to them. For the challenges that needs to be tackled to achieve the Mission, we argue that it is useful to distinguish between controllable problems (A) and uncontrollable problems (B). A concept related to uncontrollable problems that is used in the Mission, is the aforementioned ‘wicked problems’ in which high stakes, risks and/or high uncertainty are involved in a policy-relevant issue, a characteristic of the ‘post-normal condition’—that is, a circumstance in which scientific facts and social values are difficult to untangle.³⁰

3.1.2 *Why engage with citizens? The theory and terminology behind citizens*

From the very beginning, the EU Missions have been designed with the underlying principle that their success will depend on the participation of citizens, appropriate to the issue at hand^{31,32}. This goes hand in hand with the philosophy of post-normal science. There are several reasons why a more participatory approach including citizens can be understood as necessary. One reason is a normative one, often referred to as the ‘**deliberative turn**’.³³ The deliberative turn is defined as follows in Dryzek, 2002: “*The deliberative turn represents a renewed concern with the authenticity of democracy: the degree to which democratic control is substantive rather than symbolic, and engaged by competent citizens.*”³⁴ The deliberative turn argues that we should democratize knowledge and expertise, not only regarding who consumes it, but also who produces it. Hence, participatory approaches are needed to assess what knowledge is relevant and who manages the validity and relevance of that knowledge. In this view, all (not just scientists) can have relevant knowledge and experience that can be useful for the Mission.

The term ‘**citizen**’ can be quite vague and is used differently across different fields (legal, political), projects, and policy areas. In general, when used in this toolbox, ‘citizen’ emphasises the non-specialist, non-elite nature of the individuals in question³⁵. This creates some distinction from the sometimes-overlapping term stakeholder (also often used throughout Mission Ocean & Waters literature). **Stakeholders**, by contrast, may be either specialist, elite, have access to the Mission activities due to their employment, or some other form of contextual privilege. They also tend to be represented as organisations or interest groups, while citizens tend to be engaged as individuals. That said, the two concepts often overlap and, of course, individual stakeholders can also be citizens, and citizens may be stakeholders. And the tools provided in this toolbox can be applied to either or both.

³⁰ Funtowicz & Ravetz (1993)

³¹ Mazzucato (2018)

³² Mazzucato (2019)

³³ Dryzek & Niemeyer (2019)

³⁴ Dryzek (2002)

³⁵ Chwalisz (2020)

A number of loosely linked research approaches to what participation entails have developed in recent decades. Here, we understand **citizen participation** to occur when individuals from diverse backgrounds and expertise engage with knowledge-production and/or decision making in a collective endeavour. This can be a range of activities, including knowledge-production initiatives, political events in which decisions are to be made, or the conception, development and implementation of a societal Mission. Citizen engagement and citizen participation is used interchangeably in this guide. It may also be referred to as community engagement, citizen involvement, public engagement or civic engagement.

Note that citizen participation does not necessarily require formal citizenship, but refers to the general public or residents, in a specific area. Citizen participation is crucial not only to grant legitimacy, credibility and salience³⁶ to a Mission, but also to realize democratic values and social justice³⁷. Moreover, citizen participation allows for a wider and more diversified knowledge base, which is important to cope with the uncertainty and ambiguity inherent to addressing the Mission, and to ensuring the salience of the solutions proposed.

3.2 Types of engagement to consider, depending on risk and desired outcome: Steps of participation from informing to empowering

Before planning any project, leaders like you must ask some key questions to ensure that your goals are achievable. In the case of engaging citizens in the Mission, we should first ask: *When* should we involve citizens and/or stakeholders? *Why* are we seeking their participation? And finally—and most importantly—given the type of problem we're addressing or the form of participation we're inviting: *How likely is it that this will lead to meaningful outcomes?*

These questions are not only strategic—they are ethical and epistemic. The answers shape whose voices are heard, what kinds of knowledge are valued, and how risk and uncertainty are handled. In complex and uncontrollable situations, such as climate adaptation or health crises, it becomes crucial to reflect on who is included, whose knowledge counts, and how different forms of uncertainty are mapped and negotiated throughout the process—from problem framing to final decisions.

Moreover, in contexts marked by irreducible uncertainty, normative disagreement, and a lack of consensus on standards, open public debate isn't just helpful - it's necessary. It enhances the legitimacy of the process and ensures that diverse perspectives are accounted for, even when agreement is elusive. A pertinent example is the Covid-19 pandemic, where decisions on public measures had to be made amidst deep uncertainty and competing values. The way participation was handled shaped both the perceived justice of outcomes and the public's willingness to accept them.

In short, meaningful participation depends not only on when and why we involve people, but on how thoughtfully we navigate uncertainty, inclusion, and legitimacy throughout.

3.2.1 What is citizen participation?

Participation may entail a range of involvements, for example, from differing levels of communication (receiving information or voicing opinions) to directly impacting how a research process unfolds or what the outcomes are. While the avenues for participation vary in function and intensity, it is a

³⁶ Cash & Belloy (2020)

³⁷ Bennett et al. (2021)

widespread agreement that participation should grant a greater degree of power to citizens. The principles of participation are typically illustrated as a ladder³⁸ which describe a spectrum of engagement depths and their corresponding levels of citizen power (see Figure 6 below). In this toolbox, we visualise the ladder of participation as a **matrix** to better reflect the relationship between what people can expect with different forms of engagement. In the matrix, increasing levels of engagement means greater citizen power. To the far right of the matrix – or at the top of the ‘ladder’ – citizens have the power to define the problem, develop the solution and the process to get there. Different types of ladders have served as a basis for informing processes of citizen participation and as inspiration for further developing guides for participation.

The matrix can be used to assess the level of engagement for different participatory processes. While there may be good reasons to include citizens, it is important to underline that not all problems require the greatest levels of involvement – this depends on the type of problem at hand. Different types of problems demand different participatory strategies. This toolbox distinguishes between **controllable** problems—those with clear risk profiles and known solutions—and **uncontrollable** problems—those characterised by complexity, uncertainty, or ambiguity. In theory however, higher engagement levels and more decision-making power delegated to citizens should lead to greater perceptions of legitimacy and public trust in the decision-making process. Since high levels of engagement requires a substantial commitment by citizens, ensuring the relevance of the problem to be solved is key. Inviting citizens to participate in defining the problem, may thus enhance the success of your citizen engagement initiative.

³⁸ Arnstein (1969)

		DEGREE OF CITIZEN DECISION-MAKING POWER				
		INFORM	CONSULT	INVOLVE	COLLABORATE	EMPOWER
PARTICIPATION GOAL		To provide the public with balanced and objective information to assist them in understanding the problem, alternatives, opportunities and/or solutions.	To obtain public feedback on analysis, alternatives and/or decisions.	To work directly with citizens throughout the process to ensure that public concerns and aspirations are consistently understood and considered.	To partner with citizens in each aspect of the decision, including the development of alternatives and the identification of the preferred solutions or activities.	To place final decision-making in the hands of citizens.
	PROMISE TO THE PUBLIC	The Mission initiative will keep citizens informed.	The Mission initiative will keep citizens informed, listen to and acknowledge concerns and aspirations, and provide feedback on how public input influenced the decision.	The Mission initiative will work with citizens to ensure that their concerns and aspirations are directly reflected in the alternatives developed and provide feedback on how public input influenced the decision.	The Mission initiative will look to citizens for advice and innovation in formulating solutions and incorporate advice and recommendations into the decisions to the maximum extent possible.	The Mission initiative will implement what citizens decide and/or co-lead and co-lead initiative.

FIGURE 6. PARTICIPATION MATRIX: A LADDER ADAPTED TO REFLECT PROBLEM COMPLEXITY AND EXPECTED CITIZEN POWER.³⁹

There are both benefits and limitations to different participatory approaches⁴⁰. For instance, sharing of responsibility (e.g., to ensure that participation is more than lip service⁴¹), classification of who relevant stakeholders or citizens (together referred to as ‘actors’, due to the parts they play) are, as well as addressing the vested interests and power differences implicated in a given process⁴². In reality, multiple challenges often arise with participatory approaches: who to include and how to include citizens in different processes; are they interested in participating at all? This is often referred to as ‘stakeholder’ or ‘engagement fatigue’ in participatory processes. Reasons for this type of fatigue varies, but is typically related to time constraints, language barriers, different priorities, poor personal reward or little capacity/power to influence decisions⁴³.

Risks are an intrinsic part of human life and must also be considered when designing your project. In modern times, many risks that society faces are the unintended consequences of the development and application of new technologies such as global warming and pollution⁴⁴. Other issues are beyond our understanding and control, and uncertainty cannot necessarily be reduced. There are many ways to conceptualize risks. We suggest categorizing different risk phenomena as **simple**, **complex**, **uncertain** and **ambiguous risks**. These exist on a continuum and should be understood as such also for the Mission-related initiatives. Our knowledge about systems or technologies varies. **Simple or linear risks** can be described as those that are better understood and easier to model than others and

³⁹ Adapted from [IAP2 International Association for Public Participation \(2014\)](#).

⁴⁰ Wachinger & Renn (2010)

⁴¹ Linke et al. (2011)

⁴² Buanes et al. (2004)

⁴³ See for instance Jönsson & Swartling (2014)

⁴⁴ Beck (1992)

can therefore be better risk managed (if the resources are available). For these issues, one can calculate risks on the basis of established scientific models and historical patterns of performance, for example, weather patterns, sea currents and so on. Other issues are more **complex or even uncertain**, for example, new technology or tightly coupled systems that increases complexity and non-linearity and hence risk. For instance, the effects of new fisheries gear technology on the ecosystem can cause effects that were impossible to predict. With **ambiguity**, we here refer to the plurality of legitimate viewpoints for evaluating decision outcomes and justifying judgements about their tolerability and acceptability.⁴⁵ Note that with new knowledge, methods and experience, a risk may change from ambiguous to any of the other categories. The Covid-19 pandemic is an example of an ambiguous risk which is (better) controlled with new knowledge, experience and methods. How to judge the different types of risk are culturally contingent – they are cultural products since they depend on perceptions about what is probably, unlikely, serious or absurd. Accordingly, there is no one correct answer or interpretation of risks, nor solutions⁴⁶.

3.2.2 Visualising your project as steps of participation: From informing, to empowering, considering project goals and risks involved.

In order to support the process of choosing what type of involvement is necessary for different Mission-related problems, we will use the two types of problems introduced in Section 3.1.1. above; A) controllable and B) uncontrollable problems, as a rough diagnostic tool. The more uncontrollable the problem that a project is tackling, the more ambiguous the scope of risk becomes, and the type of participation we require can be related to this continuum – in the type of knowledge we require, the relevant actors to provide it and ultimately the level of participation. We particularly recommend active, two-way participation when dealing with uncontrollable problems—especially because these situations often require involving different types of actors, depending on the nature of the problem.

To help with this, we propose a diagnostic tool to help visualise the ‘steps of participation’, from informing to empowering participants, which can be defined to reflect the type of information a problem or project requires; from which relevant actors. Figure 7 below helps to visualise the concept that controllable problems are related to simple risk and can be used to help assess when it is most appropriate to inform, consult or empower citizens. **Uncontrollable problems** span a continuum of **complex, uncertain, and ambiguous risks**. The goal of engaging citizens in the Mission is to empower them to take responsibility and action toward the overarching aim: restoring our ocean and waters. But The Mission itself is a complex and uncontrollable challenge, with a broad and sometimes ambiguous scope of risk. So, where do different parts of *your* project fit along this continuum, and what ‘step’ (or steps) of the citizen participation ladder should you be aiming for?

⁴⁵ Wachinger & Renn (2010)

⁴⁶ Burns & Machado (2010)

FIGURE 7. DIAGNOSTIC TOOL FOR PARTICIPATION LEVEL. VISUALISING THE STEPS OF PARTICIPANT ENGAGEMENT FROM INFORMING TO EMPOWERING, ACCORDING TO SCOPE OF RISKS AND EXPECTATIONS WITHIN PROJECTS.

Note that citizen participation is always possible at all levels of risk⁴⁷. The controllable problem goes down a continuum to uncontrollable problems from the left to right; while the expected level or type of participation is illustrated going from the bottom up. If the expected participation is knowledge input as one-way information (inform) it suffices to include scientists in the participatory processes. Moving further to the right towards uncontrollable problems, the expectations for the type of participation changes and involves consultations with civil society, including feedback to the process to scientists/policy makers. This depends on the problem at hand, however, as practice experts such as fishers, farmers, *etc.*, may have relevant knowledge input.

3.2.3 Managing expectations of citizen participation

Two of the expected outcomes of Mission Ocean & Waters with respect to citizen participation includes the application and development of **deliberative democracy** mechanisms – that is, the inclusion of citizens in deliberative processes (Table 5). In this section we will briefly address common expectations of what can be achieved by participatory processes and the already mentioned deliberative turn⁴⁸ (see Section 3.1.226).

In general, deliberative democracy has faith in consensus and that “public reason-giving is the best way to uncover what is good and true”⁴⁹. The deliberative turn⁵⁰ has been criticized by many^{51,52} and it is important to maintain realistic expectations of what can be achieved and what challenges can arise. One assumption of deliberative democracy is that broad participation in decision-making will bring about more legitimate and effective policy outcomes⁵³. For example, ensuring citizen participation in Mission Ocean & Waters initiatives should lead to increased legitimacy. But legitimacy

⁴⁷ Adapted from Bjørkan (2011)

⁴⁸ For a more detailed discussion on the issue, see Noguera et al (2022)

⁴⁹ Lövbrand et al. (2011)

⁵⁰ Dryzek (2002)

⁵¹ Mouffe (2000)

⁵² Pløger (2004)

⁵³ Bäckstrand (2010)

is difficult to measure since it is not directly observable; and even if something is perceived as legitimate, it can be both inefficient and inequitable. Another assumption is that broad participation will ensure consensus. But failing to acknowledge dissensus can lead to shallow or disappointing outcomes^{54,55}, especially in the post-normal context (see Table 6), and when the end-result creates winners and losers^{56,57}. Hence, we warn against holding consensus as the ‘holy grail’ of success. Still, one can aim for consensus as an elusive target but create a space in which there is high tolerance for respectful conflict. Such an approach involves making explicit the multiple values underlying the conflict, as well as generating an atmosphere of respectful disagreement. As such, arenas for participation should be organized in line with the *ideals* of deliberative democracy, even if they may be hard to put to work in real life. For instance, it is an ideal that the deliberation process between citizens should take place in a space free from manipulation and the exercise of power⁵⁸. However, people will have different relations to each other and the authorities no matter where you are and who you place together – some will have formal power, and some will have informal power.

3.3 Who? Tools for helping to decide which citizens to involve, and why

In this section we describe the process to be taken after deciding what level of participation is needed. The advice provided here is based on experiences from participatory processes realized in several projects.

As addressed in the previous sections, there are many good reasons for supporting citizen participation, and it is important to think critically about which level of participation is necessary and what expectations will come along with each concrete case. Citizen participation has some practical and analytical weaknesses which are important to consider. For instance, it is practically impossible for all citizens to participate directly in workshops or meetings; most people have little time and no desire to participate in technical decision making such as wave forecasts.

Thorough preparation in advance of actual instances of citizen engagement is crucial for successful implementation. The complexity of socio-environmental-economic challenges of our times have led to increased demands for citizens to participate in decision making, policy production, governance, and research. While this is positive from a democratic and social justice perspective, demands for time and engagement from citizens are increasing⁵⁹. Therefore, it is essential to carefully consider the reasons for calling citizens to participate, as well as how their engagement will unfold. This mitigates ‘engagement fatigue’⁶⁰ and lays the ground for a more productive and successful process. The guiding reflection questions in Table 7 are meant to support in the preparations and considerations for citizen participation initiatives.

A key aspect of preparation is relationship building and communication with the target community/stakeholders. This is essential to ensure that the future process is understood and requires more than sending periodic email updates, invites and reminders. For example, community

⁵⁴ Hillier (2003)

⁵⁵ Barry & Ellis (2010)

⁵⁶ Bjørkan & Rybråten (2019)

⁵⁷ Bjørkan & Veland (2019)

⁵⁸ Lövbrand et al. (2011)

⁵⁹ Attree et al. (2011)

⁶⁰ Clark (2008)

leaders and key stakeholders could be identified, sought out, and engaged in some preparatory activities like stakeholder mapping of specific target groups, or communication strategies to the general civil society. Trust is built through such interactions as well as (perhaps especially) the informal chatting that takes place around such activities. Such an approach creates partnerships with key stakeholders, community leaders, or local figureheads that can be tasked with promoting the future engagement process themselves. This usually leads to much deeper engagement from the target community, a better understanding of the issues as people themselves verbalise them, and generally a more successful process.

3.3.1 Guiding Questions

It is important to consider several aspects including:

1. **Power** – focus on who is in a position to influence in the given context. Power can take different forms: a) *Utilitarian power* is based on control over material resources or incentives (e.g., funding agencies, industries with economic leverage); b) *Normative power* stems from moral authority, cultural values or perceived legitimacy (e.g., environmental NGOs, Indigenous communities); c) *Coercive power* involves the ability to enforce rules or impose sanctions (e.g., regulatory bodies, law enforcement). It is equally important to identify actors who may **lack power** yet are deeply affected by the issue at hand.
2. **Legitimacy**, focusing on who has a legitimate right to influence. This can be based on tradition (fishers, for instance) or employment (aquaculture, for instance), how representative they are (formal vs informal).
3. **Urgency/need** for immediate attention
4. **Economic status**. Stakeholders can have an urgent need to influence problems that have an irreversible element (threaten life, reduce quality of life, threaten economic security, threaten biodiversity, or destroy cultural heritage). This aspect also includes vulnerable groups; and
5. **Practicalities**: in general, practicalities cannot be ignored since budget, time and practical consideration will limit the selection of stakeholders. This includes issues such as: what is realistic? Do we have easy access to stakeholders? Are stakeholders willing to participate? Are there any risks?

Table 7 below provides some guiding reflection questions to help prepare your project. It is not meant to lead to a final answer, rather to instigate reflections and guide the process of defining your goals for citizen participation.

TABLE 7. GUIDING REFLECTION QUESTIONS FOR PREPARING FOR CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT.⁶¹

	Guiding questions/suggestions	Comments
Framing your project	What is the focus area of the project?	For instance, coastal zone planning or waste disposal?
	What type of problem are you dealing with?	Controllable / Uncontrollable (See Part 3, Section 3.1.1 if you are uncertain)
	What is the scope of risk?	Simple/complex/ uncertain/ambiguous (see Section 3.1.3 and Figure 7).
	What do you hope to obtain by including citizens in your project?	Define your goals, objectives and expected results, for different parts within your project. (see participation goals in Figure 6)
Planning who should participate	Map your participants, to define the different relevant actors you need to provide different types of input, at different levels of participation.	See Figure 7 and use the participant mapping template below (Table 8) to guide this. More detailed stakeholder mapping tools are available in Appendix 1.
	Consider the <i>Leave No One Behind</i> principle	After mapping your participants, consider who might be left behind? Why? And is it appropriate to try to overcome these barriers of engagement? If so, how?
	If activities have a high level of complexity in terms of engagement, you may divide them into sub-problems with corresponding sub-activities	This will allow stakeholder identification and engagement at sub-activity level.
	Place activities in a timeline. Do some activities depend on the implementation of other activities?	At what stage should citizens be engaged in my project? Consider barriers, including stakeholder fatigue and external demands on their time.
Pre-planning for evaluation What is your desired impact?	Consider methods carefully	Are the methods selected appropriate? (see Part 5).
	How will you know if planned engagement and methods are working well?	Think about essential metrics early – will you evaluate this qualitatively or quantitatively?
	What is the desired impact of the engagement process on project results?	How will you evaluate this? You can use different types of tools to gather this information e.g., e-mail, survey or workshop.
	What is the desired impact of engagement for participants?	How will you evaluate this? You can use different types of tools to gather this information e.g., e-mail, survey or workshop.
	How can you learn through the project, review and adapt methods/ approaches / participants?	How?

⁶¹ Questions adapted from Zimmermann and Maennling (2007), and Durham E., Baker H., Smith M., Moore E. & Morgan V. (2014). The BiodivERsA Stakeholder Engagement Handbook. BiodivERsA, Paris (108 pp)

3.3.2 *Participant mapping*

Mapping participants (Table 8 on the following page) is important in order to get an overview of who you aim to include, and who you actually manage to include. Given the *Leave No One Behind* principle, effort should be taken to ensure gender and equality issues are reflected upon. For instance, if you are alone with small children, it can be difficult to participate in meetings during the afternoon; and if you don't have a car, you may not travel far, and there may be identity/religious/historical reasons for avoiding buildings such as churches. It is also important to consider the ethics of their inclusion, whether it is appropriate to ask for their time and whether your method of inclusion or dissemination may fuel local conflict, which could risk the success of the project or reputation of your problem.

A more detailed stakeholder mapping template, which considers power and legitimacy more thoroughly, is available in Appendix 1.

TABLE 8. PARTICIPANT MAPPING TEMPLATE. BASED ON SOURCE: EMPOWERUS PROJECT: [HTTPS://EMPOWERUS-PROJECT.EU/](https://empowerus-project.eu/)

Participant type	Name	Organization, network or interest group	Contact details (e-mail)	Brief summary of their stake or agenda	Motivation to participate	Type of input required (knowledge / experience & reflections / co-production and responsibility)	Level of participation (inform, consult, involve, collaborate or empower)	Where in project do you need participation?	When?	Barriers to participation?	Ethical considerations	Engagement types / method?
Intergovernmental												
Public National												
Public Regional												
Public Local government												
Sub-local												
Private sector												
Non-local NGO												
Citizen												
Who might be left behind?												

3.4 How? Tools for planning implementation

This section covers a range of different citizen engagement tools with explanations of the step-by-step process of implementing them (preparation, during and after). Many of the methods may apply to both stakeholder and citizen engagement, as these terms often overlap. According to your Mission Ocean & Waters initiative and the problem you are to solve, some tools are more appropriate than others, and this toolbox is not exhaustive. Therefore, we recommend reflecting on the guiding questions of Section 3.3.1 before deciding on your chosen method. We also suggest exploring the wide range of stakeholder engagement methods guides that are available online⁶².

When implementing a method, it is important to consider the power relations between organizer/researcher and participants, and between participants (when using tools that involve several citizens) (see detailed stakeholder mapping in Appendix 1). When inviting citizens to participate, think about the location that you choose for your activity. Aim for a place where participants feel comfortable. For each tool, we encourage you to reflect on the principle of *Leave No One Behind* (LNOB) and aim for inclusion and diversity in your informants⁶³.

Methods included in this toolbox (see Part 5, Sections 5.1 to 5.7):

- Survey
- Citizen’s assemblies
- Future scenario workshop
- Semi-structured interviews
- Walking interviews
- Participatory mapping
- Strategic ocean literacy as a way of working

In developing an engagement strategy, several key questions need to be addressed – a list of questions that can be useful for choosing the specific tools is provided in Table 7. Table 9 may also guide you in choosing a tool, depending on the type of problem you are dealing with, and the level of participation you are aiming for.

In Table 9 below, the participation level depends on how your project decides to involve the citizens in the process and the level of decision-making power delegated to them. That means that how your Mission Ocean & Waters initiative decides to incorporate citizen input, will determine the level of participation pertaining to each tool. For instance, if you decide to implement a citizens’ assembly, you may also delegate decision-making power in the form of voting, to the participants.

⁶² <http://actioncatalogue.eu/search>

⁶³ United Nation on ‘Leave No One Behind’: <https://tinyurl.com/bdf4rc8s>

TABLE 9. PARTICIPATION LEVEL DECISION MAKING MATRIX. (SOURCE: PROJECT PREP4BLUE).

Problem type / participation level	Controllable problem	Uncontrollable problem
Inform	Newsletters, flyers, campaigns, websites, social media etc. (traditional ocean literacy)	
Consult	Survey , Citizen’s Assemblies	Future scenarios , Semi-structured interviews , Walking interviews , Participatory mapping
Involve	Citizens’ Assemblies , Ocean literacy	Future scenarios , Participatory mapping
Collaborate	Ocean literacy	Citizens’ Assemblies , Future scenarios , Participatory mapping , Ocean literacy
Empower	Ocean literacy	Citizens’ Assemblies , Future scenarios, Ocean literacy

3.5 Why? Tools planning for impact – monitoring and evaluating citizen engagement

Evaluating the effectiveness and type of the engagement in some way is an important part of the engagement process. Monitoring and evaluating citizen engagement will provide important results, including help planning, learning from the experience, evidence to demonstrate to participants how their effort matters and evidence of value of the research process and research output^{64 65}. Which can, in turn, improve the engagement process.

Recall that in theory, civil society can be included in all type of projects/issues (e.g., defining project goals, knowledge production, advisory processes, and with different degrees of responsibility) with different levels of involvement (e.g., ownership, responsible, collaboration, exclusion). The point of monitoring and assessing citizen engagement is to illustrate how different methods will result in different levels of participation, and that critical reflection about the purpose of participation in any given project is useful. It is key to any participatory project to be explicit about what the aim of the participation is in order to avoid accusations of lip-service rather than real participation.

Monitoring and assessing the engagement processes for the Mission can take various forms. Inclusive and transparent practices are essential. The purpose of the monitoring and assessment exercise should be taken into consideration when choosing the monitoring design. Note that this is also a step that can be a matter of co-creation, reflecting relevant, recognizable, achievable and tangible results⁶⁶. In initiatives which seek to collaborate with or empower citizens, participatory monitoring and evaluation may be most suitable. It is important to consider whether it is the outcomes/impact of the engagement process or the process itself that ought to be evaluated, or both.

Accordingly, two main **categories of evaluation** can be highlighted:

⁶⁴ Nogueira et al. (2021)

⁶⁵ Durham et al. (2014)

⁶⁶ Durham et al. (2014)

- I. **Summative approaches** that focus more on the *outcomes* than on the process. For example, to demonstrate to participants how their contributions have been adopted in the Mission perspective. For this purpose, both quantitative and qualitative data can be useful.
- II. **Formative approaches** that focus on learning from the engagement *process*. For example, to describe and illustrate why and how the engagement process did/did not work. In addition, it is important to consider participants perspectives and how they view the outcomes and process.

There are different stages of evaluation: from the outset, throughout the process and final evaluations⁶⁷. Exactly when evaluation should take place is hard to define on general terms, but overall, it is important to consider and plan for monitoring and evaluation early. There is no one-size-fits-all solution, but in the following we describe some important aspects and provide some tools to monitor and evaluate citizens engagement.

Ideally, before inception or very early on in your project, you have considered the guiding questions provided in Table 7 (Section 3.3 above). Recall that as different Mission Ocean & Waters initiatives will aim to solve a variety of problems, they will all require different levels of participation and will relate to different contexts. Using the same tables before, during and after project start can be useful to reflect on your aims, and to better be able to evaluate whether those aims are met during and after the project start. Constant reflection and adaptation are keys to success in co-created projects. So regularly revisit the answers you gave in Table 7 and Table 8, in conjunction with Table 10 to plan your re-iterative evaluation strategy below. Examples of how these tables can be adapted and used are provided in Part 4.

TABLE 10. CITIZEN/STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT EVALUATION TABLE

	What do you want to know?	What evaluation methods will you use?	How will the evaluation be conducted?
Planning process			
Engagement			
Benefits/outcomes			

3.5.1 Evaluation in relation to Mission Ocean & Waters

It is useful to note, that funders often require funded projects to provide a high level, summative evaluation of their approach and impact on wider society that specifically focus on aspects of their funding criteria. As we focus here on supporting the goals of Mission Ocean & Waters, Appendix 4 provides a useful tool for planning and mapping your subsequent impact at high level on The Mission target outcomes, objectives and overarching goal. This simplified way of mapping can be adapted for any project goal, at any level.

⁶⁷ A guide to evaluating public participation: <https://tinyurl.com/92emrytz>

For more specific evaluation, we provide two additional tables below that can be adapted to evaluate your impact towards Mission Ocean & Waters:

- Table 11: Example of a table for evaluating outcomes in Mission Ocean & Waters initiatives (adapted from Warburton et al. 2025⁶⁸). The table below is filled out as an example of use.
- Table 12: Table for evaluating citizen engagement at different stages of Mission Ocean & Waters initiatives, with example applications. A detailed example of its use is provided at the end of this Section.

TABLE 11. EXAMPLE OF A TABLE FOR EVALUATING OUTCOMES IN MISSION OCEAN & WATERS INITIATIVES

Goals/purpose of your Mission initiative	Possible Indicators for your initiative	How to obtain data for your initiative	Important assumptions for your initiative
To better inform stakeholders and the general public	Increased understanding and awareness	Questionnaires and interviews with participants before and after the process	That both the awareness and willingness to engage are as a result of the engagement activity, rather than any other factors.
	Willingness to participate in the future	Questionnaires and interviews after the process, and follow-up interviews at a later date	

In Table 12 on the following page, the axis should be adapted according to your needs. Here, the horizontal axis is related to the stages, and for each of these you should reflect on the depth of engagement. This should be compared to the aims of engagement at the outset of your initiative. The vertical axis is related to Figure 7, the steps of participation.⁶⁹

⁶⁸ Warburton et al. 2025: <https://www.involve.org.uk/sites/default/files/uploads/docuemnt/Making-a-Difference-.pdf>

⁶⁹ Adapted from Bjørkan (2011)

TABLE 12. TABLE FOR EVALUATING CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT AT DIFFERENT STAGES OF YOUR PROJECT, WITH EXAMPLE APPLICATIONS

How are citizens involved in your initiative?		Stages in your Mission Ocean initiative:				
Eg: Knowledge-based policy making process, e.g. engaging fishers in contributing data for fisheries management		<i>Planning /design</i>	<i>Data collection</i>	<i>Data analysis</i>	<i>Advice</i>	<i>Management</i>
Eg: A context outside policy-making, such as local habitat or species restoration projects		<i>Design creation</i>	<i>/ Develop-ment</i>	<i>Implemen-tation</i>	<i>Monitoring</i>	
Add your initiative here		Stage 1?	Stage 2?	Stage 3?		
Depth of citizen involvement	Active (involve, collaborate, empower)					
	Responsive (consult)					
	Passive (inform)					

Examples of how these can be adapted and used are provided in Sections 4.1 and 4.2.

3.5.2 Evaluating impact on societal ocean literacy

Increasingly, funding calls related to the Mission ask for ocean literacy to be embedded within the project. As a result, Appendix 4 provides a simple planning template through which you can plan the goals and anticipated outcomes of your ocean literacy activities and prompts to help start thinking about the best methods of evaluation. Figure 8 gives an example of how this can be used to inspire planning your activities around the known dimensions of ocean literacy (presented as a method in Section 5.7, Figure 13) and suggestions of ways to start more detailed formative evaluation.

FIGURE 8. MAPPING THE AIMS AND IMPACT OF OCEAN LITERACY WITHIN A PROJECT - AN EXAMPLE OF WORKING WITH WATER QUALITY ACROSS STAKEHOLDER GROUPS. BASED ON THE 7 ESSENTIAL PRINCIPLES OF OCEAN SCIENCE (NMEA, 2024), AND 10 CURRENTLY ACCEPTED DIMENSIONS KNOWN TO IMPACT OCEAN LITERACY (MCKINLEY ET AL. 2023).

4 Part 4: Examples of projects engaging with the citizen participation targets of Mission Ocean & Waters

The European Commission's ambition in relation to citizen engagement with Mission Ocean & Waters falls under a handful of clear themes – working with ocean literacy approaches within PREP4BLUE pilot action projects (Section 4.1), ocean literacy networks (Section 4.2), fisheries management (Section 4.3), or engaging the European Solidarity Corps (Section 4.4), or citizen assemblies (Section 4.5). Overall, this section has been written to provide examples and advice on achieving these citizen participation aims, and aligning with the requirements of the [Mission Ocean & Waters Implementation Plan](#) and with themes that have characterised the yearly Horizon Europe Missions Work Programme funding call topics.

4.1 PREP4BLUE pilot projects: aimed at engaging citizens in activities related to ocean preservation, pollution prevention, and fostering a sustainable blue economy

In May 2024, PREP4BLUE advertised a Pilot Action⁷⁰ for projects with the objective of facilitating or developing success stories on citizen engagement and mobilisation towards the objectives of the Mission Ocean & Waters Implementation Plan, which could be replicated or scaled up in the future. Six varied projects were selected for the fund, and tested the tools presented in this toolbox. A full summary of the projects is provided in PREP4BLUE's publication: [A co-created portfolio of mission-relevant pilot activities to support evaluation of project tools and methods](#)⁷¹. Each project was offered the opportunity to meet with toolbox developers and discuss how to implement parts of the toolbox, so that we could improve the tools provided in future. In this section, we present selected real-life examples of how some of these projects adapted these tools to plan, deliver and evaluate their projects. It is important to note that all projects found the guiding questions provided in Table 1 or Table 7 ('Questions to ask your project during planning stages' very useful early in their project development.

4.1.1 *Guiding questions used to prepare for the Us: Sea of Sounds immersive virtual reality project, Norway*⁷²

The Us: The Sea of Sounds pilot action, co-funded by PREP4BLUE, aimed to raise public awareness about underwater noise pollution and its impact on marine ecosystems, specifically cetaceans. Using virtual reality technology, the project offered participants an immersive experience of marine soundscapes in the Vestfjord (a prototype), enabling them to understand how noise pollution affects species like whales and dolphins. The project also included educational workshops, live listening

⁷⁰ PREP4BLUE funding call for Pilot Action Awards to engage citizens in Mission Ocean & Waters: <https://prep4blue.eu/prep4blue-pilot-activity-funding-engaging-citizens-in-mission-ocean/>

⁷¹ Pelegrí et al. (2025)

⁷² Excerpts taken from the PREP4BLUE Pilot Action Report produced by Michal Lovecky from the Go360 s.r.o., and republished here with permission.

stations, and large-format images to provide a comprehensive learning experience. The key objectives were to engage the public in marine conservation, foster understanding of noise pollution, and strengthen local community involvement.

PHOTO 1. IMMERSIVE, GAMIFIED CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT THROUGH VIRTUAL REALITY, ENABLING USERS TO UNDERSTAND HOW NOISE POLLUTION EFFECTS THE MARINE ENVIRONMENT AS PART OF THE US: SEA OF SOUNDS PROJECT. PHOTOGRAPHY BY MICHAL LOVECKY FROM THE GO360 S.R.O.

The project used a selection of the PREP4BLUE tools, presented further in Pelegri et al. (2025). Their process was guided first by their clear ambitions to work towards Mission Ocean & Water citizen engagement target outcomes (Figure 9, adapted from Appendix 4).

FIGURE 9. MAPPING OF THE US: SEA OF SOUNDS PROJECT ONTO THE EU MISSION RESTORE OUR OCEAN AND WATERS CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT TARGET OUTCOMES, UTILISING THE MAPPER PROVIDED IN APPENDIX 4.

The project development was informed by thoughtful reflection and adaptation of the guiding questions provided in Section 2.2 / 3.3 (Table 1 / Table 7) as presented in Table 13.

TABLE 13. GUIDING QUESTIONS USED BY THE US: SEA OF SOUNDS PROJECT TO DEVELOP THEIR PROJECT PLAN, UTILISING TOOLS PROVIDED IN TABLE 1 / TABLE 7 OF THE PREP4BLUE TOOLBOX.

Guiding questions	Comments
What is the focus area of the project?	Engaging citizens in raising awareness of underwater noise pollution and its impact on marine life through VR.
What type of problem are you dealing with?	Uncontrollable (marine noise pollution).

What is the scope of risk?	Complex & Uncertainty (multiple stakeholders, ecological, and social impacts).
What do you hope to obtain by including citizens in your project?	Increase public awareness, promote marine stewardship, and gather experiential feedback.
Define what type of input you will need in order to succeed	Co-production and reflection (citizen feedback, stakeholder expertise).
Who are the relevant actors?	Scientists, development team, local volunteers, cultural institutions, local businesses, the general public, and international visitors.
What level of participation do you aim for?	Involve & Collaborate; Active participation in feedback, co-design, and public engagement.
Place activities in a timeline. Do some activities depend on the implementation of other activities? At what stage should citizens be engaged in my project?	Mainly during the main event, with some input during prototyping (weeks 2-4) and post-event feedback (weeks 6-7).
Questions before and during start of project	Comments
What type of participation is our aim?	Interactive participation, with citizens co-designing and providing feedback on marine conservation efforts.
What depth of participation do we want?	A balance between experiential engagement through VR and reflective participation via interviews and workshops.
How can we pinpoint exact type and level of participation?	On-site semi-structured interviews, observation of emergent behavior, feedback collection.
Are the methods selected appropriate?	Qualitative methods: semi-structured interviews, observation, and feedback forms worked but were constrained by time.
What is working well/not working well and why?	Playtesting and VR feedback loops were successful; however, limited time and high demand restricted in-depth post-experience discussions.
What is the actual impact of the process on the results?	Feedback directly informed rapid VR iterations during the event, improving user experience.
What is the actual impact of the process on the participants? (do they feel empowered?)	Participants felt more informed and engaged but lacked time for deeper reflection due to queues for the post-VR exposure. The presentation followed by the workshop worked better in this.

Careful planning of how the project would evaluate its outcomes in relation to Mission Ocean & Waters (Table 14, adapted from Table 11) resulted in both high levels of engagement and positive and measurable feedback from participants on the user experience of both the technology, and their increased awareness of the impact of underwater noise.

TABLE 14. EVALUATION OF THE OUTCOMES OF THE US: SEA OF SOUNDS AGAINST THEIR MISSION OCEAN & WATERS OBJECTIVES, USING THE TEMPLATE PROVIDED IN TABLE 11.

Goals/Purpose of your Mission initiative	Possible Indicators	How to Obtain Data	Important Assumptions
To better inform stakeholders and the public	Number of participants; Increased awareness and understanding	Pre- and post-event interviews; workshop discussions	That awareness changes are due to the engagement, not external factors
Promote co-design and active participation	Number of participants involved in co-design activities	Participation records, feedback forms	That participants feel their contributions are valued
Empower participants for future engagements	Willingness to engage in future projects	Follow-up interviews	Continued engagement is directly linked to the project's activities

4.1.2 Consideration of the ladder or participation and evaluation tools by the Sea Synergy Oyster Project, Ireland

Excerpts taken from the PREP4BLUE Pilot Action Report produced by the Sea Synergy Marine Awareness, Research & Activity Centre, and republished here with permission.

This Pilot action funded by PREP4BLUE involved delivering a showcase of the key findings of the Sea Synergy Oyster Project (SSOP) to date and an engagement section through holding a public consultation with the community on their thoughts, hopes and concerns for future *Ostrea edulis* reef restoration in their channel and helped formulate what this action would look like in the future. Actions were taken with the aim to:

- 1) Increase the local community's ocean literacy & connection to their coastline;
- 2) Increase in citizen science reporting of marine biodiversity;
- 3) Empowered coastal community to participate in local nature restoration plans.

SSOP utilised the 'steps of participation' diagnostic tool to think about what level and type of involvement they needed from different stakeholders and citizens for their project to be successful (Figure 10 adapted from Figure 3 / Figure 7). They also considered the *Leave No One Behind* principle, which resulted in a more diverse array of engagement opportunities across the project to engage minority groups and socially disadvantaged groups through collaboration with existing Tidy Towns (a

well-known and popular community competition, driven by the Department of Rural and Community Development) & Fairseas initiatives (a coalition of Ireland’s leading environmental non-governmental organisations and environmental networks).

FIGURE 10. APPLICATION OF THE ‘STEPS OF PARTICIPATION’ DIAGNOSTIC TOOL TO ASSESS CITIZEN AND STAKEHOLDER PARTICIPATION NEEDS WITHIN THE SEA SYNERGY OYSTER PROJECT, IRELAND. FIGURE ADAPTED FROM FIGURE 3 / FIGURE 7 OF THIS PREP4BLUE TOOLBOX.

The project team also thought strategically about stakeholder engagement, both in terms of inviting participation and by way of informing the community of the results. They found novel channels and means of advertising, including championing from a local comedian and social media influencer, targeted invites through relevant instant messaging services and groups, and local newspaper coverage.

The project team thought further about the depth of their involvement, adapting Table 12 to assess the type of their engagement, revealing that they had active, and hopefully empowering involvement in the development, implementation and monitoring of their co-created restoration project (Table 15 below).

TABLE 15. BASIC EVALUATION OF CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT AT DIFFERENT STAGES OF THE SEA SYNERGY OYSTER PROJECT, IRELAND, ADAPTED FROM TABLE 12 OF THE TOOLBOX.

Depth of citizen involvement	Design / creation	Development	Implementation	Monitoring
Active (involve, collaborate, empower)		X	X	X
Responsive (consult)	X	X	X	X
Passive (inform)	X	X	X	X

This project team found that early consideration of how they would evaluate their project (Table 16 below) meant that they collected useful and positive feedback from their participants about their involvement in the process, which informed later stages of the project.

TABLE 16. A PARTICIPANT ENGAGEMENT EVALUATION TABLE WAS USEFUL AT THE OUTSET OF THE SEA SYNERGY OYSTER PROJECT TO PLAN A STRATEGY THROUGH WHICH TO ASSESS THE SUCCESS OF THE PROJECT (BASED ON TABLE 10 OF THIS TOOLBOX)

	What do you want to know?	What evaluation methods will you use?	How will the evaluation be conducted?
Planning process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What the community knew on the topic before VS after our showcase event. • What the community thinks of the project and what shape they want it to take in the future. 		
Engagement		World Café discussion and Feedback forms	The world café discussion will be conducted after showcasing key finding of project and feedback forms will be handed out at the event and sent digitally and responses will be anonymous.
Benefits / outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More ocean literate community • Pride of Place • Increased citizen science recording • Co-design of how the project progresses 	Open casual environment for discussion and ability to give feedback or share concerns anonymously	Conducting discussion after talk sharing key findings will mean people are sharing opinions on a project they have a better understanding of. Feedback forms being both digital and physical make them more accessible.

Furthermore, they were able to map the outcomes onto Mission Ocean & Water objectives (Figure 1, using the template provided in Table 11). Pre and post event surveys found that the showcase events influenced the participants knowledge about local oysters, and an increased awareness (and enthusiasm) that connected people to a habitat that is often out of sight / beyond the reach of many people.

Goals/purpose of your Mission project	Possible Indicators for your project	How to obtain data for your project	Important assumptions for your project
Showcase the key findings of the project to date to improve understanding of <i>O.edulis</i> and channel among community	Improved understanding	Pre and Post event surveys	That both the awareness and willingness to engage are as a result of the engagement activity, rather than any other factors.
Collaborate with the community to decide how the project will progress	Active involvement in discussion and willingness to engagement in the future	Feedback Survey & open discussion	
Increase citizen science reporting in the area using the project on iNaturalist.	Engagement in the iNaturalist Project	Stats automatically generated by iNat informing us about the number of observers, identifiers and observation.	

FIGURE 4.7. EVALUATION OF THE OUTCOMES OF THE SEA SYNERGY OYSTER PROJECT AGAINST THEIR MISSION OCEAN & WATERS OBJECTIVES, USING THE TEMPLATE PROVIDED IN TABLE 11).

PHOTO 2. IMAGES FROM THE SEA SYNERGY OYSTER PROJECT IN ACTION. PHOTO BY ANNA KELLAGHER FROM THE SEA SYNERGY MARINE AWARENESS, RESEARCH & ACTIVITY CENTRE

4.1.3 Participant and Mission Ocean & Waters impact mapping used by the arts-based participatory project, Sustainable Coastal Futures – Institute for Art and Innovation (IFAI), Germany

Excerpts taken from the PREP4BLUE Pilot Action Report produced by the Institute for Art and Innovation (IFAI) and the Coastal Union Germany/H2Mare Project. www.art-innovation.org/project page <https://universal-sea.org/prep-4-blue> Republished here with permission.

The 'Sustainable Coastal Futures: An Interdisciplinary Workshop and Social Media Initiative on Green Energy and Citizen Participation' pilot action was launched in August 2024. The initiative aimed to engage citizens and stakeholders in co-creating future scenarios for sustainable ocean use and coastal management, with a focus on green coastal energy production, particularly offshore hydrogen. A key

component of this project was fostering social inclusion and enhancing acceptance of green coastal energy solutions in the North and Baltic Sea regions.

This pilot action supported Mission Ocean & Water's goals for 2030, emphasizing the restoration of marine ecosystems and the transition to a carbon-neutral blue economy.

Key objectives and goals were:

1. Foster social inclusion by involving citizens in co-designing future scenarios for ocean sustainability and green coastal energy.
2. Bridge communication and knowledge gaps between citizens, policymakers, industry, and academia, and creating actionable solutions for sustainable coastal development.
3. Explore new methods of engagement using arts-based engagement tools, such as future scenario planning and visualization, to inspire action and collaboration.

To maximise success, this arts-based project chose to focus heavily on their participant mapping, utilising and adapting the templates provided in Section 2.2 / 3.3 (earlier versions of Table 1 / Table 7). They adapted this table in Figure 11 to focus on 1) who the participants were, their roles, interest and power in the process; 2) what were each of their needs and motivations to take part in the participatory process; 3) the key messages they needed for each in their engagement strategy and 4) their potential contributions to the project.

1. Who are the stakeholders?

Stakeholder Group	Sub-Groups	Roles	Interest in the Project	Influence/Power
Citizens and Local Communities		Co-creators, provide local insights, represent community needs	High interest: directly affected by green hydrogen policies, ecosystems, and local economies	Medium
Environmental Organizations		Advocates for biodiversity protection and ecosystem restoration	High interest: promote ecosystem resilience and ensure minimal environmental impact of new technologies	High
Academic Institutions		Provide scientific expertise on ecosystem health, climate change, and renewable technologies	High interest: research opportunities and practical applications for sustainability	High
Industry Representatives		Developers and implementers of renewable energy and green hydrogen solutions	High interest: advancing production technologies, infrastructure, and market acceptance	High
Policymakers		Observers, potential decision-makers incorporating citizen insights into policy frameworks	Medium interest: aligning policies with societal and environmental goals	High
Cultural Institutions		Hosts and facilitators of workshops; promote cultural and environmental heritage	Medium interest: engage the public and foster awareness of coastal ecosystem importance	Medium

2. What are their needs and motivations?

Stakeholder	Needs	Motivations
Citizens and Local Communities	Clear communication of benefits/risks, opportunities to participate in decision-making	Desire to have a voice in the future of their communities and ensure economic and ecological balance
Environmental Organizations	Transparent environmental assessments, inclusion in green energy discussions	Commitment to preserving biodiversity and promoting sustainable practices
Academic Institutions	Access to data, opportunities for collaboration, and real-world applications for research	Advancing knowledge, applying research to practical challenges, and fostering interdisciplinary collaboration
Industry Representatives	Public acceptance, efficient implementation processes, and clear policy frameworks	Advancing green hydrogen technologies while ensuring local and societal acceptance
Policymakers	Data-driven recommendations, citizen input, and alignment with national and EU sustainability goals	Creating policies that balance innovation, environmental preservation, and social inclusion
Cultural Institutions	Engagement tools, increased public participation in workshops and cultural events	Promoting awareness of environmental heritage and fostering community engagement

3. Stakeholder Communication and Engagement Strategies

Stakeholder Group	Engagement Strategy	Key Messages
Citizens and Local Communities	Direct invitations, participatory workshops, social media outreach	"Your voice shapes the future of your community and coastal environment."
Environmental Organizations	Collaborative scenario-building sessions, targeted discussions on biodiversity	"Protecting ecosystems ensures sustainable coastal and economic futures."
Academic Institutions	Knowledge-sharing forums, co-creation of scenarios, and data visualization exercises	"Science drives actionable and sustainable solutions for coastal management and energy transitions."
Industry Representatives	Interactive dialogue, scenario testing, and participatory prototyping	"Innovative technologies can work in harmony with local ecosystems and communities."
Policymakers	Presentation of workshop outcomes, policy recommendations informed by citizen input	"Citizen-driven scenarios provide actionable pathways to achieving regional and national sustainability goals."
Cultural Institutions	Workshops, guided tours, and post-event engagement through exhibitions and media	"Cultural heritage and sustainable innovation go hand in hand in fostering environmental stewardship."

4. What is their potential to contribute to the project?

Stakeholder	Contribution
Citizens and Local Communities	Local insights, participation in co-creation, and ongoing advocacy for sustainable solutions
Environmental Organizations	Expertise in ecosystem protection, ensuring environmental considerations are embedded in solutions
Academic Institutions	Scientific data and methodologies, facilitation of scenario-building and evaluation
Industry Representatives	Technical expertise, feasibility assessments, and resources for implementing green hydrogen solutions
Policymakers	Adoption of recommendations, policy alignment, and funding opportunities
Cultural Institutions	Hosting, public engagement, and promotion of environmental literacy

FIGURE 11. MAPPING PARTICIPANT NEEDS AND ENGAGEMENT ACROSS THE SUSTAINABLE COASTAL FUTURES PROJECT, ADAPTING TABLE 1 / TABLE 7 OF THE PREP4BLUE TOOLBOX

Additionally, the Sustainable Coastal Future project considered the *Leave No One Behind* principle, and took the following measures to maximise involvement of individuals with limited access to decision-making forums (including youth and marginalized communities): targeted invitations through social media and local networks; inclusion of students and young participants in the workshop; simplified tools like mood boards and visual aids to ensure accessibility for non-experts, showed in Photo 3 below.

PHOTO 3. TEMPLATES, MOOD BOARDS AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TOOLS WERE AMONGST THE METHODS USED BY THE SUSTAINABLE COASTAL FUTURES PROJECT TO INSPIRE DIALOGUE AND INVOLVEMENT OF PEOPLE WITH DIFFERENT SKILLS, ACCESSIBILITY NEEDS AND INTERESTS.

The Sustainable Coastal Futures project resulted in collaborative visualisations of a future coastal ecosystem that included both narrative and artistic elements to represent sustainable green hydrogen infrastructure coexisting alongside restored mangroves and oyster reefs (Figure 12 below). The project also considered how to work with the dimensions of ocean literacy, which you can read more about in Pelegrí et al. (2025).

FIGURE 12. COLLABORATIVE VISUALIZATIONS OF A FUTURE COASTAL ECOSYSTEM CO-CREATED WITH PARTICIPANTS OF THE SUSTAINABLE COASTAL FUTURES PROJECT. THIS OUTPUT COMBINES NARRATIVE AND ARTISTIC ELEMENTS TO REPRESENT SUSTAINABLE GREEN HYDROGEN INFRASTRUCTURE COEXISTING WITH RESTORED MANGROVES AND OYSTER REEFS.

4.2 Ocean Literacy networks and campaigns as a tool for citizen engagement

An ocean literate society is one that ‘understands what the ocean does for us, and what we can do for the ocean’. It has been dubbed as the key enabling factor behind the success of the UN Ocean Decade, that strives to deliver ‘the science we need for the ocean we want’. Initially, ocean literacy was grounded in 7 Essential Principles of ocean science⁷³, and aimed to educate / inform the public and the marine and maritime stakeholders of knowledge of these Principles in a top-down approach. However, the evolved concept of ocean literacy⁷⁴, grounded in the science of behavioural change and adoption of a system approach, aims at facilitating the creation of an ocean literate society who will, in turn, take better care of our shared ocean. An increasing number of researchers^{75 76} recognise that knowledge alone will not result in behavioural change and went on to define the following ten dimensions known to influence ocean literacy: awareness; knowledge; attitudes; communication; behaviour; activism; access and experience; ‘emoceans’; adaptive capacity; trust and transparency.

4.2.1 *Why use Ocean Literacy as a tool for citizen engagement with the Mission?*

A major part of the evolved concept of ocean literacy is grounded in two-way dialogue, bottom-up and participatory processes that start to give citizens more decision-making power. Ocean literacy has moved beyond delivering knowledge to school children, to instead acting as powerful conversation starters with a range of citizens to gain varying types of input – from gathering their feelings towards blue spaces for development or restoration, to informing private homeowners of their responsibility to handle drainage properly. Ocean literacy is an important two-way participatory approach, or even method, that can be used strategically by projects working towards Mission Ocean & Waters, particularly to meet their citizen engagement target outcomes.

4.2.2 *How to integrate Ocean Literacy into Mission Ocean & Water projects and related activities?*

More detail on how to use ocean literacy as a method for citizen engagement in Section 5.7. The proposed method uses the aforementioned dimensions of ocean literacy to both plan participatory processes with different citizen groups (Figure 8) and / or as a way of evaluating the impact of your project on society’s relationship with the ocean (Section 5.7). If you are considering using ocean literacy methods or approaches, this is a rapidly evolving field, with many toolboxes and research papers being released, with new ideas of how to improve our ways of working. New networks or assemblies are also being created, and you can consider the relevance for your project to engage with these networks – either as researchers or as practitioners. For example, networks around people linked to the sea through responsible sport activities, arts or activism (such as the EU Projects [Blue Genes](#) and [Blue Mission AA](#)), there are a specific groups for marine educators (e.g., [the European Marine Science Educators Association](#)), and there is a [Global Ocean Literacy Research Community](#).

⁷³ NMEA (2024)

⁷⁴ McKinley et al. (2023)

⁷⁵ Brennan et al. (2019)

⁷⁶ McKinley et al. (2023)

A big effort should be made in ensuring that you have a well classified repository of initiatives or activities depending on the target public, expertise and length. And that any resources and outputs are planned with ‘legacy impact’, in how and where they are stored and made available for other projects. Engaging with networks is one way to do this. The [Future Seas 2030](#) project provides an excellent summary of resources, networks and guidance in the supplementary materials of their 2022 paper.⁷⁷

Some examples of the founding and high-level toolboxes are provided here:

- [Ocean literacy for all: a toolkit](#) IOC. Manuals and guides
- [Ocean Literacy: The Essential Principles and Fundamental Concepts of Ocean Sciences for Learners of All Ages](#)
- [Ocean Literacy Framework](#)
- [Ocean Literacy Scope & Sequence for Grades K-12](#)

4.2.3 Case Study: The Irish Ocean Literacy Network and supporting cross-border collaboration through ocean literacy

This example highlights the use of storytelling and scenario-based workshops to explore complex water management issues through local citizen engagement.

The Irish Ocean Literacy Network (IOLN) is the working name of an informal network established in 2016, aimed at bringing together individuals and organisations who are currently involved in, or would like to become involved in, working towards the IOLN vision, which is to achieve an Ocean Literate society across the Island of Ireland. Galway Atlantiquaria, National Aquarium of Ireland, is the current Secretariat of the IOLN, and in this role it acts as a central contact and dissemination point for the Network supporting initiatives and collaboration opportunities between the IOLN members and providing a platform for engagement with relevant stakeholders.

Since its inception, the IOLN has hosted many networking events, workshops, etc., including the ‘We are islanders’ national campaign. The Network has also become recognised internationally as an advocate of ocean literacy and is involved in large scale initiatives like the UNESCO Ocean Literacy With All, the EU4Ocean Platform, the EuroGOOS Ocean Literacy Working Group, and is part of both the All-Atlantic and the European Blue Schools Network. As part of these initiatives, in June 2022 the IOLN was one of the ten organisations to sign the Charter for Blue Education in Europe developed within the frame of the EU4Ocean Coalition and its Network of Blue schools, whereas in October 2022 the IOLN participated to the 2nd Ocean Literacy Dialogues event held in Brazil.

The IOLN is one of the ocean literacy networks involved in the Horizon Europe project PREP4BLUE with the aim to contribute to the project’s work focused on enabling stakeholders to empower citizen and community-led action in support of Mission Ocean & Waters. To facilitate this, the IOLN organises a yearly series of regional members meetings in the four provinces of the Island of Ireland, i. e. Connacht, Leinster, Munster and Ulster, the aim of which is to give the Network members the opportunity to come together in person to exchange ideas and discuss future plans for common ocean literacy initiatives after the long break caused by Covid. The first of these meetings was held in Belfast

⁷⁷ Kelly et al. (2022)

in 2023, and it gave the attendees the opportunity to reflect on the value of the all-Island nature of the Network and to discuss how to best proceed in order to foster the establishment of new cross-border ocean literacy-focused collaborations. Also, the IOLN is supporting the first specific objective of the Mission ‘protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity’ via the establishment of a working group within the Network itself focused on key marine ecosystems under threat, like, for example, seagrass meadows and coastal dunes. The role of this working group will be to bring together the different community groups active across the Island on conservation projects focused on these special environments to promote dialogue among them and facilitate an exchange of information, resources and opportunities

4.2.4 Case Study: EmpowerUs: embedding ocean literacy as a method across a transdisciplinary research and innovation project in six countries.

The EU Horizon project [EmpowerUs](#) committed to deliver ocean literacy resources and activities across its case study communities. However, as the project strove for ‘Socio-economic Empowerment of coastal communities as users of the sea to ensure sustainable coastal development’, it utilised ocean literacy as a research tool and to improve participation, open dialogues and ultimately tested its efficacy as a mechanism towards empowerment. The co-development of resources and activities was informed by researchers studying participatory processes to reveal potential transitioning needs for coastal communities facing changes. The methods followed were similar as those outlined in Section 5.7 and will be soon available on the project website⁷⁸ and related publications⁷⁹. In summary, some of the processes involved:

- Co-creation of treasure hunts which developed into cultural ‘story’ trails to explore island residents’ connection with the coast and sea. These in turn were adopted by national NGO and became illustrated hiking trails, raising the profile of island-sea connection.
- Household leaflet campaigns providing positive narratives and knowledge about surrounding coasts, signposting funding opportunities and offering dialogues with homeowners about creating their own marine spatial plans around their coastal residencies.
- Workshops to understand marine identities in connection to coastal developments.
- Food sovereignty workshops, participatory / community voice videos and exhibitions to involve locals and foreign residents in local marine protected area dialogues.
- Co-creation of ‘women making waves’ campaign, showcasing how local women were empowered by the sea; which will be developed into children’s activity booklets and disseminated across the 6 local communities.

The project also worked with the wider Ocean Literacy Research Community to develop an international survey instrument, *The Ocean & Society Survey*, to assess the ten dimensions of ocean literacy, at local and national scales. This tool is now available to help inform your project development, or for you to use one or all questions from in your local context^{80, 81}. The data will also be made freely and publicly available in 2025.

⁷⁸ <https://empowerus-project.eu/news-and-events/>

⁷⁹ Morris-Webb et al. (2025 in press)

⁸⁰ McRuer et al. (2025)

⁸¹ <https://oceanliteracyresearch.com/ocean-and-society-survey/>

4.3 Fisheries management: Monitoring how and whether fishers are included in the assessment of cod stocks.

Fish stock assessments are crucial for sustainable fisheries, but relying solely on scientific data has had negative outcomes—most notably, the collapse of Canada’s cod fishery. Involving fishers in knowledge production is seen to improve both the accuracy and relevance of assessments, as their practical knowledge complements scientific expertise. Norway’s Institute of Marine Research (IMR) launched the Norwegian Reference Fleet (RF) as a pioneering initiative to involve fishers in fisheries management. The fleet consists of selected vessels that collect standardized data, serving as a reference point for scientific analysis.

According to Figure 6 (Citizen Participation Spectrum), fishers can participate at different levels and stages of knowledge production: data collection, assessment, and advice. Table 17 below illustrates this with a matrix: the horizontal axis shows stages of knowledge, and the vertical axis represents the degree of responsibility or decision-making power. Three types of fisher participation are outlined:

1. **Working with science** – Fishers cooperate with scientists on tasks like data collection. This is the most accessible form of involvement and helps build trust.
2. **In addition to science** – Fishers contribute independent knowledge or advice, which may differ from scientists’ assessments.
3. **Taking responsibility for knowledge** – Fishers are accountable for specific knowledge functions in management. This model exists in countries like New Zealand, though it doesn’t mean fishers do everything themselves.

4.3.1 *Evaluating the Reference Fleet Using Table 17*

The table serves as a diagnostic tool to evaluate how fishers are involved and at what level of responsibility. The more stages and levels of participation covered, the deeper the inclusion.

In practice:

- **Data collection:** RF fishers collect valuable biological data used in national and international assessments. However, their role is limited—they follow predefined protocols and do not influence what or how data is collected. Their contribution is akin to that of a technician, with minimal decision-making power.
- **Assessment:** Fishers are not involved in this stage. It remains a closed, expert-driven process carried out by scientists from institutions like the IMR.
- **Advice:** The RF does not involve fishers in producing management advice. This remains the responsibility of the International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES).

Although the RF may seem modest compared to its ambitious framing, it marks a meaningful shift in a system where fishers were previously excluded from knowledge production. It reflects incremental but significant progress, particularly from the perspective of the fishing community. To further strengthen fisher involvement, projects can use Table 17 to identify where and how participation could be deepened across more stages and with greater responsibility.

TABLE 17. EXAMPLE OF A TABLE USED TO MONITOR AND ANALYSE HOW FISHERS (STAKEHOLDERS) HAS BEEN INCLUDED IN STOCK ASSESSMENT THROUGH THE ESTABLISHMENT OF THE NORWEGIAN REFERENCE FLEET. FOR MORE DETAILS, SEE BJØRKAN (2011).

How fishers' are knowledge included		Stages of Stock assessment		
		Data collection	Assessment	Advice
Level of Responsibility	Working with science	X	0	0
	In addition to science	0	0	0
	Responsibility for	0	0	0

4.4 Leveraging the European Solidarity Corps to achieve the aims of your Mission Ocean & Waters initiative

The below examples show how youth volunteer programmes can be mobilised to support hands-on citizen engagement, from coastal restoration to education and advocacy, while aligning with EU Mission objectives.

4.4.1 What is the European Solidarity Corps?

The European Solidarity Corps (ESC) is a European Commission (EC) initiative that provides opportunities for youth to contribute to a range of solidarity projects around Europe through voluntary action⁸². A range of topics are covered by ESC projects, including disaster risk reduction and preparedness, migrant community work, and nature protection⁸³.

Organisations can register their project with the ESC portal and apply for funding. These projects may be short term (2 weeks to 2 months) or long-term (2 to 12 months). If successfully funded, projects are then matched with volunteers through the ESC portal.

Young people between 18 and 30 years old can register to be part of the pool of volunteers by creating a profile in the ESC portal, where they can find projects to join. An individual can only take part in a maximum of 12 months of total volunteering. Their travel and living costs are funded by the EU⁸⁴.

The ESC programme focuses on sustainable development, social inclusion, and equal opportunities, and one of their priority areas is "Environmental Protection, Sustainable development and Climate

⁸² Associazione Joint Milano. (2019, March 1)

⁸³ European Union. (n.d.). *About*. European Youth Portal.

⁸⁴ Erasmus+ Project. (2021, June 4). *European Solidarity Corps*.

Action”⁸⁵. Examples of European Solidarity Corps-funded projects related to the marine and freshwater environments are:

- [Make it Blue – European Solidarity Corps in Action](#)
- [MarSius Blanca](#)
- [Proyecto CETUS](#)
- [Save the Nature Save Our Future](#)
- [Ochrancovia riečnej krajiny](#)
- [Costa degli Dei Clean up](#)
- [ECO Superheroes – Keep Costa Tropical Clean](#)
- [EcoSmart](#)

To get an overview of all the types of projects that the ESC is involved in, have a look at ongoing and completed projects here: <https://youth.europa.eu/solidarity/projects/>

4.4.2 *Why involve the European Solidarity Corps in your Mission Ocean & Waters initiative?*

First of all, including the ESC in Mission-related activities is one of six expected outcomes in terms of citizen engagement that the Mission requires by 2025. It has also been reflected in multiple calls in the Horizon Europe Work Programmes for the Mission in 2021-2022, and 2023-2024. **Engaging with the ESC, then, is a key way of aligning a project with Mission aims**, and a funding application with call requirements.

By registering your organisation with the ESC programme, you will be able to apply for funding to develop your Mission Ocean & Waters initiative, and if accepted, get access to volunteers who are ready to contribute their skills and efforts around Europe. If you are not a local organisation, working with young locals through the ESC can also be a way to better connect and cooperate with local communities in which you want to work. Additionally, it is possible to apply to become a partner in an already existing project through the ESC portal. Given that the ESC programme is funded by the European Commission, projects that align with the EU Missions, including Mission Ocean & Waters, should be well oriented for support by the ESC.

Mission-funded projects may also find value in reaching out to ESC projects that are already up and running, or to volunteers/organisations from those that recently finished. Doing so can produce learnings and recommendations that will help in the design of future projects and help optimally align the ESC with the EU’s new Mission framework.

Whether you want to involve youth as volunteer facilitators in your citizen engagement activity, as helping hands in a restoration project, as citizen scientists, or as co-managers of a community led project, the ESC portal is a great resource for reaching them.

⁸⁵ European Solidarity Corps. (2022, February 4).

4.4.3 *How to involve the EU Solidarity Corps in your Mission Ocean & Waters initiative?*

In order to apply for funding from the European Solidarity Corps and involve volunteers in your Mission project, read the [European Solidarity Corps Guide](#) and follow the 8 preparation steps listed on their website: https://youth.europa.eu/solidarity/organisations/before-you-apply_en.

Note: The European Commission also provides guidelines for beneficiaries of the European Solidarity Corps on how to communicate and promote their project achievements from the planning phase through the evaluation phase. The guide is open access, and provides useful communications tips, even for projects that are not funded by the ESC. The guidelines can be found here:

https://youth.europa.eu/news/new-communication-guidelines-project-beneficiaries-released_en

4.4.4 *Example of ESC project: MarSÍus Blanca, Catalonia, Spain*

This project illustrates place-based engagement through youth-led action, combining environmental education, local restoration, and citizen science within a marine conservation context (Start date: 01-06-2022 / End Date: 31-05-2023).

MarSÍus was a European Solidarity Corps project carried out by young locals with the support of Globers, youth organisation around Comarruga, in the south of Barcelona. This project was created to cultivate the sense of responsibility and love for the coastal ecosystem among the local community and the tourists that come to the area during summer. Due to the ecological importance of the area – home to Catalonia’s only marine reserve, called Masía Blanca – MarSÍus has been a project to raise awareness about the importance of protecting our coast and sea, involving different organisations and public institutions who have been working together with the Globers team to support participation, active citizenship, and grow community through marine protection projects.

Project Activities:

Together with the collaboration of Anellines and Goven 2.0, Onada Foundation, University of Barcelona and Globers, activities include:

- Diving to map the seafloor in search of Posidonia oceanica meadows
- Support to the study of marine micro plastics for the University of Barcelona
- Cleaning beaches of garbage and plastics
- Cleaning of dunes, taking off invasive plants and repopulating with native plants

Some key achievements of the project have been:

- Improvements to the marine environment
- The collection of knowledge concerning the local marine environment
- The generation of significant engagement of the local community
- The bonds created among different organizations that work for the protection of the sea and public institutions.

*‘MarSÍus has given to me the opportunity to experience that when you feel love for the sea, there is hope for a blue future. It is a matter of transmitting this love’
– Paula García Rodríguez, ESC volunteer and ESC Coach with Globers.*

About **Globers**: Globers is a youth organization that puts all their energy and love in giving opportunities to young people, mostly through Erasmus+ and ESC programs, and supports the local community with many different activities. Their mission is to inspire, educate and mobilize young people to raise their voices while creating real change through volunteering, non-formal education and active citizenship. For more information, you can contact: globers.paula@gmail.com

Websites:

- <http://www.globers.net/>
- www.facebook.com/globers.net
- www.instagram.com/we_are_globers
- <https://www.youtube.com/c/Globers>

4.5 Recommendation: Establishing a network of Citizens' Assemblies for Mission Ocean & Ocean.

In Section 5.2 we introduce the concept of Citizens' Assemblies (CAs), as a method by which to consult and involve citizens in decision making. In this section we introduce the benefits of creating, or joining, networks of CA across geographic regions specifically focusing on Mission Ocean & Waters.

This section outlines key recommendations for creating an EU-wide network of CAs to engage the public in Mission Ocean & Waters. It also makes the case for why the significance of such assemblies extends far beyond the Mission's thematic focus. In light of the growing momentum around deliberative democracy across Europe, we support ongoing calls for the European Commission (EC) to establish permanent infrastructure for transnational CAs. Such a network would offer inclusive and sustained participation in tackling complex environmental challenges—such as ocean health, biodiversity, and climate resilience—while empowering citizens to shape Europe's environmental future.

CAs provide structured platforms for deliberative participation. Their core strength lies in bringing together a diverse group of citizens to engage in informed dialogue, and to make recommendations that are both legitimate and actionable. While most existing CAs are temporary and locally anchored, new efforts—such as the EU-based Knowledge Network on Climate Assemblies (KNOCA) - are working to connect them and promote shared learning. Building on this momentum, a permanent, Mission-aligned CA network could significantly enhance public understanding and ownership of the Mission Ocean & Waters objectives.

However, setting up such a cross-border network presents several challenges. There are currently no best-practice models for EU-wide CA coordination, and significant gaps exist in terms of institutional anchoring and sustainable funding. This section explores these issues through insights from European initiatives, interviews with practitioners, and analysis of recent CA innovations such as the Global Citizens' Assembly on the Ocean. We focus particularly on two key obstacles: (1) the lack of experience with strategic, transnational public forums on shared resources; and (2) the absence of durable structures to support long-term participation. To explore how to overcome these obstacles, the section is structured around four operational dimensions:

1. Ownership and financing
2. Participant selection
3. Deliberation and voting protocols
4. Follow-up and policy impact

Each of these elements offers practical pathways for designing, implementing, and sustaining an EU-wide CA network. We conclude with a roadmap for embedding these assemblies in the Mission ecosystem, and outlines how the EC, national governments, and civil society can co-create a durable, inclusive infrastructure for democratic engagement in marine policy. Given the emphasis placed on engagement and knowledge co-creation by the upcoming European Oceans Pact, such an infrastructure could be leveraged far beyond the lifetime of the Mission.

4.5.1 Method and data collection

To explore how CAs can support Mission Ocean & Waters and how a European-wide network might be established, we used an approach combining mapping, interviews, and literature analysis.

- **Mapping existing networks and support structures**

We first identified and mapped organisations that support, coordinate, or facilitate CA processes across Europe. This included organisations operating in Germany, Austria, Denmark, Ireland, and Belgium. Our mapping focused on understanding their role in setting up CAs, the scope of the assemblies, and how they connect to broader governance frameworks (Table 18).

TABLE 18. OVERVIEW OF ORGANISATIONS SUPPORTING CITIZENS’ ASSEMBLIES (CAS) ACROSS EUROPE

Country	Organisation	Role in CA Process	Scope of Assemblies	Connection to Governance Frameworks
Germany	[e.g. Mehr Demokratie]	Facilitates and advises on CA design	Local to national	Advises Bundestag; links to democratic innovation policy
Austria	[e.g. FIDE – Forum für demokratische Entwicklung]	Coordinates regional CAs	Regional and thematic	Works with Länder-level government and policy units
Denmark	[e.g. Danish Board of Technology]	Designs, implements and evaluates CAs	National, EU-level projects	Interfaces with ministries and EU Mission projects
Ireland	[e.g. Irish Citizens’ Assembly Secretariat]	Organises and manages official CAs	National	Embedded in parliamentary system; reports directly to Oireachtas
Belgium	[e.g. G1000]	Develops innovative models for CA	Experimental/democratic innovation projects	Influences city-level and regional decision-making

- **Interviews**

We conducted semi-structured interviews with experienced CA practitioners and representatives from key organisations, including:

- KNOCA (Knowledge Network on Climate Assemblies).
- Mehr Demokratie (Germany).
- Klimarat (Austria).
- Democracy X (Denmark).

These interviews provided rich insights into practical considerations, emerging best practices, and lessons learned from national and regional assemblies.

- **Review of literature and emerging global initiatives**

Our work also draws on relevant academic and grey literature, including evaluations of previous CAs. We paid particular attention to recent developments such as the Global Citizens’ Assembly on the Ocean, which held its inaugural meeting in Barcelona in April 2024. As part of the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development, this initiative aims to engage citizens in over 100 countries ahead of the 2025 United Nations Ocean Conference.

In addition to interviews and literature analysis, we also incorporated insights from the PREP4BLUE Citizen Engagement Webinar Series – Session 5 (“Best Practice Training for CA Facilitators”), held in March 2024. This session offered a practice-based perspective on how to support CA’s within Mission Ocean & Waters, drawing on experience from Lighthouse projects, facilitation experts, and Mission partners. Notably, the final 20 minutes of the webinar featured a lively panel discussion on challenges and solutions for building a European-wide CA network. These reflections provided timely, practitioner-led input that helped validate and refine our analysis of support structures, logistical considerations, and facilitation strategies. The full recording is publicly available via the [PREP4BLUE YouTube Channel](#).

This methodological approach provided a foundation for analysing how a transnational CA network could be effectively designed, embedded in EU and Mission Ocean & Waters governance structures, and made operational for Phase 2 of Mission Ocean & Waters and beyond.

4.5.2 The value of CAs for engaging citizens

Citizens’ Assemblies derive their strength from structured, inclusive deliberation. They place authority in the hands of citizens, giving ordinary people an opportunity to influence complex policy decisions⁸⁶. Central to this process is dialogue—creating spaces where diverse perspectives are aired, respected, and reconciled. Deliberation leads not necessarily to full consensus but to broad consent: collective recommendations that participants support, even if not everyone agrees entirely⁸⁷. This approach ensures both legitimacy and collective buy-in for recommended actions⁸⁸.

⁸⁶ Setälä & Smith (2018); Farrell et al. (2018)

⁸⁷ Lorenzoni et al. (2025)

⁸⁸ Boswell et al. (2022)

Beyond their policy influence, CAs profoundly impact participants. As one interviewee explained:

What we realize is that those who participate in a CA become empowered. They gain knowledge, their awareness grows, and they often become more active. In Austria, participants even founded an association, and some have since become politically active in their communities.

– Interview, Ines Omann, Klimarat (Austria)

CAs are particularly valuable for addressing complex, gridlocked’ issues—such as environmental or climate policy—where political institutions may struggle to act. By functioning as mini-publics, they bring together a microcosm of society, providing recommendations that reflect collective reasoning and lived experience. This process generates legitimacy, which in turn can catalyse political momentum⁸⁹.

Democratic infrastructure like KNOCA and other networks rest on the belief that democracy flourishes through participation. Strengthening dialogue across Europe not only improves decision-making but also reinforces social cohesion and trust. CAs help reinvigorate democratic engagement and can act as bridges between institutions and communities⁹⁰.

In the context of Mission Ocean & Waters, CAs could offer a dynamic, public-facing tool to mobilise citizen support, integrate and emphasise local knowledge, and ensure public perspectives help shape research and innovation priorities related to marine governance.

4.5.3 *The promise of an EU-Wide CA network for Mission Ocean & Waters*

A network of Citizens’ Assemblies would provide a structured foundation to the Mission’s “Public Mobilisation and Engagement” Cross-Cutting Enabler. The ocean is a shared resource, deeply intertwined with our climate, economies, and daily lives. It sustains livelihoods, regulates weather patterns, and holds vast ecological and cultural significance. Yet, ocean governance often remains distant from those most affected by it. A coordinated CAs network could bridge this gap. It would give citizens from diverse backgrounds a structured, participatory pathway to shape ocean and water policies. It could do this while creating links between local aquatic issues and activities, national initiatives, Mission Ocean & Waters projects, and EC marine and water policy and governance bodies.

As governments work towards more effective sustainable ocean management, they are starting to realise a need for more local inclusion of a wide variety of citizens and contexts: from co-management measures, local action and / or support / buy-in. While EU frameworks set broad objectives, implementation varies by country and region. A European network of CAs would bring together national and local initiatives, creating pathways for citizen voices to influence decision-making at multiple levels. As the EC finalises the European Oceans Pact—a strategic initiative aiming to transform ocean governance—there is a clear opportunity to embed participatory mechanisms from the start. A network of CAs could contribute bottom-up insights and legitimacy to this process, reinforcing the Commission’s focus on people-centered governance.

At a practical level, this network could function as a distributed infrastructure, embedded or otherwise facilitated regionally by the Mission’s Lighthouse projects. It would serve not only as a conduit for

⁸⁹ Farrell et al. 2018

⁹⁰ Farrell et al. 2018

citizen engagement but also as a platform for sharing best practices and engaging with shared issues across Member States. Assemblies at the basin or regional level could deliberate on topics relevant to their marine environment ranging from fisheries to marine protected areas—and feed into European-level synthesis processes.

This model would also allow for hybrid forms of participation. National or local CAs could nominate representatives to a transnational Mission Assembly. These delegates could be invited to the annual Mission Ocean & Waters Forum, which takes place each spring in Brussels, where they would consolidate and present recommendations while engaging directly with policymakers, researchers, and programme officers. Such a process would enhance vertical integration between local deliberations and EU policy cycles.

As demonstrated by recent examples—like Austria’s Climate Assembly or the Democratic Odyssey—well-designed CA structures can enable meaningful dialogue across political and cultural boundaries. By scaling these efforts through a Mission-aligned framework, the EU could create a flagship example of democratic innovation in ocean governance.

An EU-wide CA network could support bottom-up participation, connecting grassroots movements with higher-level decision-making.

While large-scale global CAs on ocean governance are still in their early stages, valuable lessons can be drawn from well-established local and national CAs. Experiences from countries such as Austria, France, Ireland, Germany and Denmark demonstrate how deliberative democracy can effectively shape climate and environmental policies. Like the ocean, the climate is a complex shared ‘resource’ of which every member of the public has a stake, and a right to an opinion. These national-level assemblies provide insights into structuring inclusive processes, engaging diverse stakeholders, and translating citizen recommendations into actionable policies.

The Global Citizens' Assembly on Marine Conservation, launched in April 2024 under the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development, represents an important step toward incorporating citizen voices in international ocean governance. Although still a new initiative, it signals growing recognition of the need for public participation in shaping major policy frameworks that will result from the upcoming United Nations Ocean Conference in 2025.

An EU-wide CA network could build on these experiences, scaling up successful national approaches while ensuring that citizen deliberations feed into both European and international policy discussions. By fostering collaboration between national assemblies and connecting them to global efforts, Europe could lead the way in integrating citizen-driven insights into ocean governance at multiple levels.

4.5.4 A transnational model: lessons from the Democratic Odyssey

The Democratic Odyssey offers a model for transnational deliberation, demonstrating how layered governance — from national to EU level — can enhance the legitimacy and inclusiveness of citizens’ assemblies. The Democratic Odyssey, launched in 2024, offers an instructive model for transnational deliberation. As a pilot for a Permanent People’s Assembly in Europe, it convened a diverse group of citizens from different EU countries in Athens to deliberate on cross-border issues, using random selection with both demographic and regional representation.

What makes the Democratic Odyssey relevant to Mission Ocean & Waters is its layered approach to governance. It combines national-level recruitment with EU-level deliberation, ensuring legitimacy

both from the bottom-up and across Member States. This model provides a compelling precedent for how Mission-related CAs could be structured:

- Local and national CAs deliberate on ocean issues relevant to their context.
- Selected representatives participate in an EU-level Mission Ocean & Waters CA.
- EU institutions and civil society ensure outcomes are taken seriously and translated into policy.

This structure recognises the shared yet context-specific nature of marine governance: while oceans transcend borders, public engagement must be grounded in local realities.

The Odyssey also showcases innovations that could be adapted for the Mission context:

- Hybrid events combining in-person and digital formats.
- Rotating regional hubs to host deliberations.
- Multi-lingual facilitation and documentation standards.

These design elements are particularly relevant for the geographical and cultural diversity of the EU's marine basins. They demonstrate how large-scale assemblies can be inclusive, flexible, and institutionally impactful.

Lessons for the Mission Ecosystem

Mission Ocean & Waters can learn three key lessons from the Democratic Odyssey:

- 1) Distributed governance strengthens legitimacy: Representation across different levels builds trust.
- 2) Permanent infrastructure matters: One-off events struggle to sustain engagement or influence.
- 3) European citizens are ready: With the right support, people across the EU can meaningfully deliberate on complex, cross-border issues.

By building on these insights, the Mission can establish a CA model that not only contributes to its 2030 goals but also helps lay the foundations for enduring public participation in ocean governance.

4.5.5 A network of Citizens' Assemblies for Mission Ocean & Waters

The two main obstacles to establishing a permanent EU-wide network of CAs—(a) the lack of experience with strategic, cross-border public forums on shared resources, and (b) the absence of permanent structures to support long-term goals—are reflected across four operational aspects that are central to the success of such a network. These four aspects— (1) ownership and financing, (2) selection methods, (3) voting procedures, and (4) follow-up processes—not only define the practical implementation of cross-border assemblies but also offer entry points for overcoming the identified challenges.

Ownership and financing are essential to ensuring long-term institutionalisation and stability, directly addressing the need for durable structures. Effective selection methods and voting procedures, meanwhile, must accommodate Europe's cultural and political diversity and are crucial for building trust and legitimacy—especially in the context of shared governance over transboundary ecosystems

such as oceans and freshwater. Finally, robust follow-up processes are needed to ensure that the outcomes of citizens' deliberations feed into policymaking and lead to sustained civic engagement—transforming ad hoc initiatives into lasting democratic practices.

The remainder of this section will explore each of these four aspects in turn, identifying practical recommendations and highlighting ways to address the structural obstacles facing an EU-wide CA network.

4.5.6 *Ownership and financing of Mission Ocean & Waters CAs*

Building a permanent network of CAs for Mission Ocean & Waters requires clear answers to the question of ownership: Who is responsible for commissioning, supporting, and responding to the work of these assemblies? And how can long-term financing be secured?

- **Institutional and citizen ownership**

Ownership operates at two levels. *First*, institutional ownership: Most CAs are commissioned by political institutions, such as parliaments or local governments, that commit to responding to assembly outcomes. Without this commitment, assemblies risk becoming symbolic or disconnected from real policy change. *Second*, citizen ownership is vital to legitimacy. Participants are more likely to remain engaged – and for recommendations to carry weight – when citizens feel they have agency and responsibility. This can be strengthened by involving citizens in planning, facilitation, ensuring broad diversity, and building confidence in the process.

For a transnational initiative like Mission Ocean & Waters, institutional ownership is more complex. With no single political authority for marine governance, coordination must be anchored in EU institutions. The EC could play a leading role by formally recognising and supporting Mission-linked CAs, ensuring their outputs are channelled into policymaking and upcoming funding priorities. If this institutional layer is not available, then stakeholder agreements - where specific organisations or governments pledge to act on recommendations - can provide an alternative model of accountability.

- **Funding strategies for Mission Ocean & Waters-linked CAs**

One-off project funding is insufficient for supporting assemblies at scale or sustaining engagement. To succeed, assemblies need adequate resources for logistics (venues, facilitation, translation), participant support (travel, accommodation, childcare), and follow-up (communication, policy dialogue, evaluation).

Previous national examples (e.g., Germany, Austria) have shown the importance of covering participant costs to enable equitable participation. This includes not only per diems and travel but also costs associated with time – ensuring those on lower incomes are not excluded.

There are several potential funding avenues relevant to Mission Ocean & Waters that could be leveraged:

- Horizon Europe Work Programmes (e.g., 2027/2028): a dedicated call topic for CAs within Lighthouses could be considered.
- European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF): funding for participatory governance.

- National or regional co-financing, particularly where marine issues overlap with local priorities.
- Public-private partnerships: industry and NGOs may wish to co-sponsor assemblies to demonstrate legitimacy and corporate responsibility while supporting action.

To ensure continuity beyond 2030, a permanent coordination function could be institutionalised within the EC. A dedicated unit under the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD) or the Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (DG MARE) (which together oversee Mission Ocean & Waters) could provide long-term support for assembly design, integration, and impact tracking. The four Mission Ocean Lighthouse basin Coordination and Support Action projects (CSAs), under their remit as regional logistical and strategic hubs, could support assemblies at local/regional level and convene them into EU-wide formats at relevant events such as the Mission Forum (see also aspect 4.5.9 below: ensuring follow-up and policy impact).

- **Building on existing Mission infrastructure**

One promising avenue for supporting CA coordination and continuity is the annual Mission Ocean & Waters Forum in Brussels. This event already provides travel and accommodation funding for Mission Ocean & Waters Charter signatories and could easily be extended to include CA participants. Lighthouse CSAs, functioning as regional coordinators, could identify and nominate CA delegates to attend the Forum and facilitate networking across Member States.

An example of Good Practice: Travel and subsistence for Mission Forum participants is already covered for certain stakeholders — this model could be extended to support citizens' assembly participants, ensuring equitable access and cost-effective implementation.

A resilient funding model should combine core institutional support, Mission-linked project financing, and multi-level co-investment. This mix would allow for both structured delivery and local flexibility.

4.5.7 Selection methods for CAs

A well-designed participant selection process is essential to ensure inclusivity, diversity, and democratic legitimacy. For Mission Ocean & Waters, this means drawing on *best practices* while adapting to the specific context of marine and transnational governance.

- **Random selection with local relevance**

Most established CAs use random stratified sampling—selecting participants to reflect demographic diversity across age, gender, geography, education, and income. For the Mission context, additional factors may enhance legitimacy and relevance:

- Proximity to marine or freshwater areas.
- Economic dependence on ocean sectors (e.g., fisheries, tourism).
- Exposure to climate and marine risks (e.g., flooding, erosion).

To promote **intergenerational justice**, the inclusion of young people is critical. Recent research and practical examples, such as Ireland's Children and Young People's Assembly on Biodiversity Loss (Harris 2021, Mallon et al. 2025), demonstrate how young citizens can contribute meaningfully while increasing the perceived legitimacy and forward-looking quality of recommendations.

- **Ensuring inclusivity**

To enhance inclusivity, active outreach is often needed beyond random invitations. Random invitations alone often underrepresent marginalised voices. Therefore, **active outreach is needed**:

- Partnerships with community organisations and schools.
- Multilingual materials and accessible formats.
- Targeted efforts to include underrepresented or hesitant groups, for example, climate sceptics, coastal labourers, Indigenous groups where relevant.

For example, Austria’s Climate Assembly intentionally included climate sceptics to ensure a broader public discourse. Such inclusive design choices enhance credibility and trust in the process.

- **Multi-level selection and representation**

Given the scale of the Mission, a multi-tiered selection structure is appropriate. Regional or national assemblies could nominate participants to EU-wide forums. This ensures territorial balance and provides local grounding for broader deliberations.

To ensure territorial and political inclusiveness across the EU’s sea basins, one approach could be to include basin-specific CAs through a dedicated call topic between 2026 and 2030. These would operate at project level, fostering basin-relevant deliberation while maintaining a common Mission Ocean & Waters framework. Alternatively, if the Mission chooses to rely more heavily on networking individual, non- Mission Ocean & Waters -funded CAs at local or member state levels, Lighthouse projects could play a key role in outreach, dissemination of the CA recommendations, and facilitating connection with policymakers at regional and EU level. These projects could identify such initiatives and invite representatives of their participant groups to engage through the Lighthouse project structures and the broader Mission Forum, thus integrating bottom-up activity into the Mission’s ecosystem.

A mixed model—combining Mission-funded basin-level assemblies with networks of independent local CAs—could reflect both geographic diversity and Mission coherence. Lighthouse projects could identify and integrate independent CAs into Mission activities, helping link bottom-up initiatives with structured EU processes.

This hybrid architecture would support both representative inclusion and flexible engagement, making the CA network responsive, durable, and scalable across Europe’s marine regions.

4.5.8 Voting procedures and deliberative culture

Effective deliberation and decision-making processes are at the heart of a successful CA. For Mission Ocean & Waters, these must be adapted to reflect the diversity of participants and the cross-border nature of marine governance.

CAs are grounded in structured dialogue, where diverse participants hear from experts, deliberate together, and formulate collective recommendations. A **key principle is consent**, not consensus. This means that decisions should reflect broad support, even if not everyone agrees fully. This fosters legitimacy while respecting differing views.

To promote robust deliberation:

- Expert presentations should be balanced and accessible.
- Facilitation must support inclusive participation and psychological safety.
- Citizens should have opportunities to reflect, question, and revise opinions.

Deliberation is enriched when civil society actors, policymakers, and scientists participate alongside citizens—offering context and realism while respecting citizen authority. Austria’s Climate Assembly used expert advisory boards, and Brussels’ regional CA involved civil servants to explain policy cycles. These formats increase both the quality and policy relevance of recommendations.

- **Voting methods that reflect diversity**

Voting procedures in CAs vary depending on national contexts, with differences in how deliberation is structured and how final recommendations are decided. Hence, CAs use a range of methods to finalise recommendations, including ranked voting, consent thresholds, or deliberative polling. For transnational assemblies, consistency matters: voting protocols should enable the aggregation of local outcomes into coherent Mission-wide recommendations. We recommend testing multiple voting methods during basin- or Lighthouse-level assemblies tailored to local contexts:

- Ranked-choice voting.
- Consent thresholds.
- Thematic clustering.

Results from these pilots could be synthesised at the annual Mission Forum. There, a final round of deliberation using an agreed method could consolidate the Mission’s annual set of citizen recommendations.

CAs hosted by the Lighthouses between 2026 and 2028 could test and refine this approach protocol. Their results would form a baseline for a durable, EU-wide CA model that is suitable to embed citizen knowledge and priorities into the implementation phase of Mission Ocean & Waters. Beyond this, the same model could be employed to similarly engage citizens in line with the aspirations of the Oceans Pact.

In short, deliberative integrity must be matched with practical consistency to ensure CAs not only work locally but also scale effectively across borders, allowing for diversity of regional contexts.

4.5.9 Ensuring follow-up and policy impact

For CAs to have real influence, their recommendations must be legitimate, actionable, and institutionally anchored. Unlike traditional decision-making, CAs do not rely on majority voting but on consent-based processes, aiming for broad agreement rather than simple majorities.

In Austria’s Climate Assembly, for example, participants worked in small groups to develop and refine recommendations before presenting them in plenary. The process emphasised deliberation and mutual understanding over quick consensus. Proposals were collaboratively adjusted, and when concerns remained, they were sent back for further revision. This helped ensure that final outcomes reflected a wide range of perspectives and enjoyed broad support among participants — which is critical for legitimacy and impact.

A key principle of CA deliberation is that participants are encouraged to consider not only their personal interests but also the broader public good. However, even well-crafted recommendations can fail to gain traction without robust follow-up mechanisms. As shown in previous cases, the level of political commitment at the outset strongly influences whether recommendations lead to change. In Austria, for instance, while regional and local implementation showed promise, limited engagement at the national level reduced the assembly’s impact on national policy.

- **Early Planning and the Role of Evaluation**

Early planning for follow-up is essential. This includes securing political commitment, monitoring implementation, and keeping citizens engaged after the assembly concludes. One proven approach is the use of stakeholder agreements — formal pledges from institutions or governments to either act on the recommendations or explain why they are not adopted. This increases transparency and strengthens trust in the process.

However, follow-up is not just about politics — it also requires a clear strategy for evaluating the outcomes and effectiveness of CAs. A recurring challenge is that funding typically ends with implementation, leaving no resources for robust evaluation. As highlighted in KNOCA’s *Impact Evaluation Framework*, while many assemblies are designed to influence policy, few include systematic tracking of whether that influence occurred. To address this, impact evaluation should be embedded from the start. This means setting clear goals, defining indicators of success, and allocating sufficient funding and staff capacity for monitoring. Evaluation should address both:

- Process quality: Was the assembly inclusive, informed, and deliberative?
- Outcomes: Did it result in policy uptake, civic engagement, or institutional change?

Within the timeframe of Mission Ocean & Waters, this evaluation work could be taken on by a dedicated citizens’ assembly project or institutionalised within the EC — for instance via DG RTD, DG MARE, or the Mission Secretariat. Alternatively, the Mission Implementation Platform or upcoming Lighthouse CSA projects could include responsibility for monitoring and evaluating CA outcomes as part of their broader oversight roles.

In addition to standard evaluation, **participatory approaches** — where citizens themselves help define what ‘impact’ looks like — could provide richer insights. These methods acknowledge that CAs often generate **transformative outcomes** that extend beyond immediate policy changes: shifts in public awareness, democratic culture, and civic agency. Such systemic impacts are especially relevant when thinking about long-term sustainability and democratic renewal. Annual reporting through the Mission Forum could synthesise this learning and inform future work programmes.

4.5.10 A Shared Framework and the Role of the Mission Forum

At the network level, a shared evaluation framework across all Mission-related CAs could support learning, comparability, and improved practice. The annual Mission Forum could serve as the central arena for presenting evaluation results and synthesising insights across the ecosystem. This would not only enhance accountability but also help align citizen input with future Horizon Europe calls and marine governance priorities.

To formalise this process, we recommend that Lighthouse CSAs and National Mission Hubs coordinate a yearly CA synthesis process. This would culminate at the Mission Forum with a dedicated citizens’ assembly session that:

- Consolidates results from national and local assemblies
- Presents regional insights to EU policymakers
- Informs the following year's Mission Ocean & Waters Work Programme

This process would create a feedback loop — allowing citizen input to meaningfully shape research and innovation funding.

- **Sustaining Engagement Beyond the Assembly**

To maintain engagement after the assembly ends, structured follow-up activities should be offered — such as funded participation in the annual Mission Forum, where citizens can reconnect, share progress, and help present recommendations. This positions CAs not as one-off events but as ongoing democratic infrastructures.

Lighthouse CSAs could take on a coordinating role by establishing regional umbrella structures that keep former CA participants engaged. These bodies could support continued communication, mobilise citizen input for new consultations, and foster a networked culture of participation. National Mission Hubs could facilitate knowledge transfer and ensure alignment between grassroots and institutional levels.

- **Mission Forum as Policy Interface**

At the EU level, the Mission Forum offers a practical, cost-efficient mechanism for linking citizen input to policy development. Travel and accommodation funding is already available for Charter signatories — extending this to CA participants would ensure broader access and reinforce the value of their contribution.

The Forum could also host structured deliberation workshops, where CA representatives work with policymakers to translate assembly outcomes into EU-level recommendations or roadmaps. These could directly influence the framing of future calls for proposals and strategic priorities within the Mission and beyond.

Similar regional events, hosted by Lighthouse CSAs earlier in the year (e.g., Arena events), could build momentum and feed into the Mission Forum's synthesis process.

- **Readiness, Inclusion, and Long-Term Impact**

Ensuring that no one is left behind — particularly groups that are harder to reach or underrepresented in traditional policymaking — requires more time and support than typical EU consultation timelines allow. For example, the public consultation on the European Ocean Pact ran for less than one month — far too short to host inclusive, well-facilitated deliberative processes.

To overcome this, the CA network should be designed to be operational early in the policy cycle and able to respond quickly when consultations open. This could include:

- A standing pool or registry of trained citizen participants.
- Agreed activation protocols.
- Early invitations from EU institutions to involve the network before key consultations close.

This would ensure that citizen deliberation is not an afterthought, but a strategic input into policymaking — both during the Mission and under the future European Oceans Pact.

- **Embedding the Legacy: A Permanent Role for CAs in EU Marine Governance**

Due to the Mission’s cross-border nature, EU institutions must play a coordinating role to connect individual assemblies to broader marine policy frameworks. To ensure sustainability, a mixed funding model will be necessary — combining EU funds, national co-financing, and public-private partnerships.

Full accessibility must be guaranteed: this includes covering costs such as travel, childcare, and time compensation, in line with the *Leave No One Behind* principle. A portion of CA funding — whether from Horizon Europe, EMFAF, or national sources — should be ring-fenced for long-term monitoring, evaluation, and institutional integration.

Ultimately, we recommend establishing a **permanent coordination function at EU level**. This would institutionalise CAs as a recognised part of marine governance, helping to ensure that public deliberation remains a lasting feature of EU environmental policy — not just a temporary experiment of the Mission.

4.5.11 Conclusion: Establishing a network of CA’s for Mission Ocean & Waters

To make CAs a lasting contribution to European ocean governance, Mission Ocean & Waters could support the creation of a permanent, structured network that aligns with its implementation roadmap and long-term vision. This could be based on a strategic integration with the Mission Ecosystem.

During Phase Two (2026–2030), focused on upscaling and deployment, the Mission is ideally positioned to embed CAs into its core architecture. A coordinated network would operate across three levels:

- 1) **Regional and national CAs** addressing or incorporating context-specific marine issues.
- 2) **EU-level Mission CA**, composed of representatives from lower tiers.
- 3) **Institutional anchors** (DG RTD, DG MARE, National Mission Hubs, and Lighthouse CSAs) ensuring uptake and feedback.

To ensure practical steps toward the establishment of a CA for Mission Ocean & Waters, key actions could include:

- Annual calls for expressions of interest from macro-regions, regions, and local communities to host Mission-linked CAs.
- Dedicated support from Lighthouse CSAs for facilitation, capacity-building, coordination and evaluation.
- Establishment of a Mission-wide deliberation and synthesis process, culminating at the annual Mission Forum.
- Annual integration at the Mission Forum: Each year, Lighthouse CSAs and a central CA coordination team organise a synthesis workshop at the Forum. This connects regional outcomes with EU-level deliberation.
- Cost-effective use of existing mechanisms: Build on existing travel and accommodation infrastructure for Charter signatories to ensure CA participation is equally supported.

Pathway to impact: Forum outcomes feed directly into the design of future Work Programmes, providing a direct route from citizen input to funding priorities. To ensure continuity, a CA coordination function should be established within the Mission Secretariat or relevant Commission services. This entity would:

- Oversee CA protocols, evaluation frameworks, and integration with Work Programme design.
- Serve as a central contact point for Lighthouse projects and external stakeholders.
- Manage long-term documentation, institutional memory, and community engagement.

Existing initiatives provide valuable models for structuring an EU-wide CA network or could themselves be used as platforms to establish an EU-wide CA network for Mission Ocean & Waters:

- KNOCA (Knowledge Network on Climate Assemblies), which has developed guidance on permanent climate assemblies and on impact evaluation,
- The Bertelsmann Foundation's proposal for institutionalizing citizen participation at the EU level,
- The Democratic Odyssey, which launched a transnational Peoples' Assembly in 2024,
- The Global Citizens' Assembly Network (GloCAN), founded in 2023, which applies lessons from the first Global Assembly on Climate and Ecology to support policymakers and organizers of global citizens' assemblies. It is funded by the European Climate Foundation, the Australian Research Council, and the University of Canberra,
- The Global Citizens' Assembly on the Ocean, launched by Missions Publiques in April 2024 as part of the UN Ocean Decade, is a precursor to a global process engaging 10,000 citizens across 100 countries, with outcomes shaping discussions at the 2025 UN Ocean Conference.

Financing and inclusion mechanisms: A blended financing model—combining EU, national, and private contributions—will be essential to sustain the network beyond 2030. All participation costs must be covered, including travel, childcare, and compensation. This is critical to uphold the *Leave No One Behind* principle.

The Mission Forum already provides a funding precedent for supporting citizen travel and accommodation. Extending this support to CA representatives—along with structured feedback loops into Mission planning—would demonstrate institutional commitment and establish legitimacy whilst enabling reflective learning and impact tracking.

A legacy beyond the Mission: By 2030, this CA network could evolve into a permanent European infrastructure for civil society engagement in ocean governance—available for use beyond the Mission timeframe, including under the European Ocean Pact and future policy frameworks.

A structured, citizen-led deliberative network would not only enhance the Mission's democratic credentials but also position the EU as a global leader in participatory environmental governance. Establishing it now is an investment in the legitimacy, adaptability, and sustainability of Europe's marine policy future.

5 Methods for citizen engagement

Methods included in this toolbox:

- 5.1 Survey
- 5.2 Citizen's assemblies
- 5.3 Future scenario workshop
- 5.4 Semi-structured interviews
- 5.5 Walking interviews
- 5.6. Participatory mapping
- 5.7 Strategic ocean literacy as a way of working

5.1 Survey

Participation level: consult.

Problem type: controllable and uncontrollable problems.

5.1.1 *Description*

Conducting surveys is a way of obtaining information from citizens which requires minimal time commitment by informants (and by you). With surveys, you may reach a greater number of informants than with other methods and, ideally, get a large representation of opinions, needs or knowledge from the respondents. Additionally, surveying requires little training, in comparison to interviewing or other methods.

5.1.2 *Preparations*

- Decide on your objective with the survey. Are you capturing quantitative or qualitative data (or both)? What will the data be used for? How will it be analysed? Is a survey the best method to obtain the desired information? Will you have open-ended, closed-ended, multiple choice, like scale questions, or a combination?
- Decide on who will be your informants and the size of your sample. If you are aiming for wide representation, you might also need a strategy for surveying similar proportions of groups as the population as a whole. Alternatively, include questions on demographic characteristics so that you later may analyse responses with proportions similar to that of the general population.
- Depending on who you want to reach, decide on the format of your survey. Is it more appropriate to conduct it online or to print for manual use? An online survey may be an easier way to reach more people, but you might also have less control over the reach of your survey. It will also depend on how 'digital' your informants are. For example, if you are asking elderly to respond, a printed form may be more appropriate. If you decide on a printed survey, have a strategy for collecting responses.
- Prepare an appropriate number of questions. Try to balance the time commitment and the amount of information you need. Many will refrain from answering surveys that look very time consuming and complicated.

- Depending on which citizens you are seeking consultation from, it could be important to include questions that will give you information on residency or affiliation to the area or region you are exploring. Consider whether your survey will be anonymous or not, and the ethical requirements that follow.
- Test your survey with someone to get feedback before distributing it to your audience.
- Include questions from which you may identify whether you are following the *Leave No One Behind* principle⁹¹.
- Write an information sheet or a paragraph that goes with the survey to describe its aims and the rights that the respondent has in terms of ethical considerations. Include your contact information in case of questions.

5.1.3 During

- If conducting an online survey: share on the communication channels you find will reach the most representative group of citizens. Share on many platforms if you require large amounts of data. If you are seeking responses from a specific group, share it directly with the group or find out where best to reach its members.
- If conducting a manual survey, investigate how and where you may reach the informants you aim to reach and how to make sure all have the same chance of responding.

5.1.4 After

- If you shared an open online survey, close the survey at the deadline. If manual, collect the survey responses as planned.
- For citizens to be informed about the outcome of their participation, share the results of your analysis and the impact of it on the platforms where the survey was distributed. If their contact information was shared in the survey, this information can also be directly shared with them. If you are open for it, give participants a chance to give feedback.

5.2 Citizen's assemblies

Participation level: Involving, collaborating or empowering, depending on how it is set up and who has responsibility and decision-making power.

Problem type: controllable and uncontrollable problems.

5.2.1 Description

Citizens' Assemblies (also called mini-publics) are often used to illustrate a method of direct deliberative democracy in a decision-making process⁹². In a citizens' assembly, citizens can come together to discuss values, concerns, opinions regarding complex challenges, such as environmental issues and climate change. Although it is argued that not all aspects of how citizens' assemblies are run can be defined as a deliberative decision-making procedure (*e.g.*, voting), there are some issues which are so value-laden that reaching consensus is an impossible goal, so there needs to be a strategy to establish recommendations. Many versions of citizens' assemblies exist, but it could generally be described as a body of randomly selected citizens that deliberate, and in some cases vote, on one or

⁹¹ United Nations on 'Leave No One Behind': <https://tinyurl.com/bdf4rc8s>

⁹² Pal (2012).

several issues that have implications at the citizen level^{93,94}. Usually, it is a value based political problem.

Citizens' assemblies may be established to improve legitimacy and public support of new and ambitious policies in line with Mission Ocean^{95,96}. This would create opportunities for the general citizen to participate in a decision-making process, for example, policymaking, and hopefully make for solutions that are more easily accepted by the public. Note that because of its relatively deep and long-term commitment, it may be challenging to get people to participate in citizens' assemblies and stay committed.

Characteristics of a citizens' assembly:

- Large (can be several hundred people, usually 100-200)
- Can be local, regional, national
- Requires a time commitment of up to one year with frequent meetings
- May be organized and sponsored by government or parliament, or civil society organisations. The Danish Citizens' Assembly on Climate Issues recommends that the assembly is established by political decision-makers who pledge to consider the recommendations in policy making.⁹⁷

More detail how networking citizens' assemblies to address the objectives of Mission Ocean & Waters is provided in Section 4.5 'Establishing a Network of Citizens' Assemblies for Mission Ocean & Waters'.

5.2.2 Preparation

- Firstly, decide on the purpose of arranging a citizens' assembly. What will the results be used for? Normally, citizens' assemblies are set up to influence policy making. What is the scale of your citizens assembly – is it local, regional, national? See also Tables 1 and 7 in this toolbox for reflection questions. It is important to decide on the expected power of influence that the assembly will have on your Mission Ocean & Waters initiative or policy. It is advisable that the sponsor of the assembly (eg., Government) makes an official, formal commitment to the ways in which the recommendations/proposals will be influencing politics or other objectives of the assembly⁹⁸.
- Set up an organizing team/overall facilitator or select an institution that will be responsible for the practical aspects of the citizens' assembly. This team should be impartial to the greatest extent possible. Facilitators could also be recruited through the European Solidarity Corps portal (See Section 4.4), but make sure they have the necessary training for supporting citizens through the assemblies and taking notes.
- The facilitator entity will plan the meetings (potentially together with members of the assembly), send out information to the members, plan presentations and invite experts, set up a voting system, and afterwards inform the members about the influence of the assembly recommendations on the policy process at hand. This team could also be responsible for reporting

⁹³ Kuntze & Fesenfeld (2021)

⁹⁴ Danish Ministry of Climate, Energy and Utilities (2021)

⁹⁵ Kuntze & Fesenfeld (2021)

⁹⁶ Dryzek & Niemeyer (2019)

⁹⁷ Danish Ministry of Climate, Energy and Utilities. (2021)

⁹⁸ Kuntze, L., & Fesenfeld, L. (2021)

throughout the assembly process and publishing results. The organizers should also inform the public about the citizens' assembly and how it is set up, as well as ensuring its transparency⁹⁹.

- Select participants. The members of the citizens' assembly should be selected randomly and be representative of the general population with regards to various demographic parameters. It could be a good idea to make the national statistics bureau responsible for the selection process, especially if the assembly is on the regional or national scale¹⁰⁰. A first step could be to survey the population on who would be interested to take part in a citizens' assembly and then have a selection process. Advertise in the communication channels relevant to your target public.
- Find a suitable location for an assembly of >50 participants (depending on the scale of your targeted region). Alternatively, set up digital meetings in a suitable and accessible platform.
- Prepare presentations or other forms of teaching (e.g., workshops) about The Mission topic, policy or project to be deliberated on, including different alternatives to be discussed. Learning materials may also be sent out before the first meeting. This is for all participants to have a knowledge base as a starting point for deliberating and advising decision-making processes. The learning material should include 'all' perspectives on the topic to be discussed in order for the assembly to understand the various viewpoints on the issue.
- Set up an expert group tasked with quality checking the education materials, balance of views in stakeholder and expert presentations *etc.*

5.2.3 During

- The citizens' assembly meetings could include a series of events for Mission Ocean & Waters issue(s) to be discussed¹⁰¹:
 - Phase 1: Readings, expert and stakeholder presentations and debates, and discussions on topics and dilemmas, as a learning phase. Develop themes for the next phase. In the case of a large number of issues, consider a voting for prioritising themes.
 - Phase 2: Working groups for each theme to develop recommendations on theme and sub-themes. These are run through a peer-review process within the assembly groups. Recommendations could also be fact checked by experts if desired.
 - Phase 3: Referendum on recommendations and compile into a report for policy makers.

5.2.4 After

- The organizing team or members of the citizens' assembly compile the recommendations into a report. This report could serve as an influence on a policy process or management strategy, depending on the purpose of the citizens' assembly. The results could for instance inform the decision-making process of the issue discussed, or be part of a policy process *etc.*

Example:

The Danish Citizens' Assembly on Climate Issues made recommendations on a range of issues, including land use, transport, popular education and agriculture, as input to the political process of

⁹⁹ Ibid.

¹⁰⁰ Danish Ministry of Climate, Energy and Utilities (2021)

¹⁰¹ Danish Ministry of Climate, Energy and Utilities (2021)

Denmark's national climate action policies¹⁰². Detailed descriptions of the process can be found in their report: [Danish Ministry of Climate, Energy and Utilities. \(2021\). The Citizens' Assembly's Recommendations. The Citizens' Assembly on Climate Issues.](#)

5.3 Scenario workshops

Participation level: Involving or partnership, depending on how it is set up and who has decision making power.

Problem type: Uncontrollable problems.

5.3.1 Description

Scenario planning¹⁰³ is a methodology with a range of processes that provide the opportunity to challenge our mental models about the external landscape that we operate within so as to inform and enhance decision-making. The methodology assists us to identify key factors in the operating landscape that are uncertain/will create uncertainty, and to understand how those factors can interplay with each other to describe plausible alternate descriptions of the operating landscape in the future. When facilitated with the intent to shape and challenge mental models, scenario planning is a powerful methodology for generating new ideas and insights that enhance decision-making. The process is not about prediction. It is about preparing us to understand and be accepting of uncertainty and complexity and to build these into our decision-making processes. The process is about developing our capacity to be able to navigate the external operating landscape in a responsive fashion.

In practice: Workshops for exploratory scenarios to co-produce knowledge with citizens/stakeholders and engage researchers. It is an inspiring way to get locally relevant narratives of change/about potential futures, to map uncertainty and to get a base for selecting robust management options.

5.3.2 Preparations¹⁰⁴

- Decide on the objective of the workshop and make a detailed program. It is useful to have a scoping phase to explore the context in which the workshop will be held. This could be done through, for example, semi-structured interviews (see Section 5.4)
- Select time and location for workshop
- Identify and invite participants (see Table 2/ Table 7/ Appendix 1). Focus on diversity of voices. Be aware of power dynamics. Invite through direct contact if available. A great way to get people to come is if you already have established contact with key people you want to invite. This could for example be through conducting semi-structured interviews ahead of the workshop (see Section 5.4).
- For reaching the general public: Posters, newspapers, social media platforms. Posters may include QR-codes linked with more info about the project/activity. It is useful to include a digital sign-up sheet in order to better plan for number of facilitators needed, and to know how much food to order. If you are restricted in terms of space and food budget, you might need to find an appropriate way to select participants and aim for a representative selection.

¹⁰² Danish Ministry of Climate, Energy and Utilities (2021)

¹⁰³ Saliba (2009)

¹⁰⁴ Nilsson et al. (2017)

- Prepare introductions. For example, a PowerPoint presentation with an introduction of your organisation and your project. Additionally, it is useful to go through a slide with the schedule of the workshop.
- Formulate focus questions for the discussions and group work (based on objective and context)
- Prepare a draft conceptual model – to inspire revisions from workshop participants
- Prepare ‘what if’-questions and wildcards/jokers (literature, scoping) to spark discussion in groups that struggle to get started with discussions
- Prepare registration and consent forms
- Prepare recommended equipment/material: Large papers/magic sheets, post-it notes, pens and markers.

5.3.3 *During*

- Introduction by facilitators (include meeting ‘ground rules’)
- Facilitated brainstorming about locally relevant drivers of change (or other topic relevant to your objective) – remember to take photos of written ideas (post-its) or record them in some other way
- Sort the ideas into categories
- Have the participants vote on for example the importance and uncertainty level of the categories from the previous steps
- Have a group work session on a topic relevant to your objective. For example: Synthesize previous steps to make a ‘model’ of local social-ecological system
- Introduce wildcards/what if-questions to spark discussion in groups that struggle to get started with discussions
- Make someone from each group report on their discussion in plenary
- Wrap-up and inform participants on the next steps of your project/initiative – invite participants to take part in writing the narratives/outcome report of the workshop
- Evaluation

5.3.4 *After*

- Synthesize: Put brainstorm insights into context of your project/initiative (e.g., basin-wide changes/marine and freshwater challenges in region)
- Revise conceptual model
- Write narratives of potential futures based on results and other relevant input
- Get comments from participants on synthesis, revised model, and narratives. Send out draft through email or other relevant communication platform.
- Evaluate workshop process and outcome (See Section 2.4 or 3.5)

5.3.5 *Steps of overall tool process*

- Scoping visits
- Identify citizens/stakeholders and concerns
- Interviews and workshop to identify relevant drivers of change
- Develop first outlook of different potential futures
- Interviews to refine narratives of potential futures

- Analysis of local input and insights from studies of changes (e.g., changes in marine/freshwater systems and biodiversity)
- Synthesize insights locally and across field sites if you are doing it several places

Example:

- Nilsson et al. (2017). Towards extended shared socioeconomic pathways: A combined participatory bottom-up and top-down methodology with results from the Barents region. *Global Environmental Change*, 45, 124-132. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2017.06.001>

5.4 Semi-structured interviews

Participation level: consultation, involve

Problem type: controllable and uncontrollable

5.4.1 Description

Semi-structured interviews are guided conversations/two-way dialogues with an open framework, often in an informal setting. It is a qualitative research method that is information rich, both in that the interviewer provides and receives information. It is a suitable method for understanding informants' perspectives, experiences and situations from their point of view. It is also a useful method to use at the planning or beginning phases of a project or initiative¹⁰⁵.

A semi-structured interview may be conducted with one informant or with a group of informants. Semi-structured interviews are more time consuming and requires more facilitation skills than a one-way, structured interview does but can be more engaging and result in information relevant to the interviewee that may widen the scope of the investigation.

Remember:

- Superfluous information may surface.
- It takes practice to find a balance between an open and a guided conversation. The interviewer needs skills or training, especially when it comes to asking non-leading questions.
- During group interviews, interruptions may occur, and the conversation may go off topic

5.4.2 Preparations^{106,107}

- Develop an interview guide with framework, topics and/or questions for conversation that covers the information you are seeking. Make sure to create open-ended questions that are not leading. Run the topics through your team and with someone who can check on the relevancy of the questions/topics.
- Make an overview of relevant informants and a procedure for selection of informants
- Practice interviews to get feedback on communication and listening skills

¹⁰⁵ Annex 1 of: Durhamet al. (2014).

¹⁰⁶ Annex 1 of: Durhamet al. (2014).

¹⁰⁷ Holm, P. (n.d.).

- Ask informants where and when they feel comfortable meeting for an interview
- Prepare the interview with precise information about the topic and other related information that might be needed during the interview
- Prepare relevant props to inspire conversation, for example maps.

5.4.3 *During*

- Greet your informant and introduce yourself in a friendly way. Be aware of your body language throughout the session.
- Assure that informants are aware of how the data will be used. Get permission to record the interview on tape or video if you will do so. Using a recorder may allow for a more natural conversation instead of the interviewer always having to look at their interview guide and appear unfocused on listening.
- Start with general questions/topics. Listen carefully and ask clear questions that may not be perceived as insensitive.
- Take brief notes to be elaborated on immediately after interview. Include notes on the atmosphere, the reactions to various questions *etc.*
- Interviewer obtains answers and can adapt their following questions accordingly. Questions from the informant will also arise during the interview – be open for questions, it is a dialogue.

5.4.4 *After*

- Analyze info at end of interviewing day. Could do this together with interview team.
- Transcribe audio recordings if you recorded the interview.
- Fact-check the interview notes with other sources or stakeholders
- Evaluate your interview guide and method to see if anything can be improved before new interviews
- Circulate results with informants for quality check, comments and feedback
- Share the impacts of interview results with your informants

Examples:

- Gómez-Ballesteros *et al* (2021). Transboundary cooperation and mechanisms for Maritime Spatial Planning implementation. SIMNORAT project. Marine Policy, 127, 104434. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2021.104434>.
- Henry *et al.* (2019). *SIMNORAT- Potential approaches for stakeholder engagement on Marine Spatial Planning and outcomes of pilot testing (D14)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.2597520>
- Nys & Bailly (2018). *Methodology guide for semi-structured interviews* (p. 20). <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25111.68002>

5.5 Walking interview/ 'go-along'

Participation level: consultation, involve

Problem type: controllable and uncontrollable

5.5.1 Description

A qualitative research method which involves interviewing *in-situ* and in-depth, connecting the informant's responses with the spaces where they practice their work or recreational activities (in a context familiar and comfortable to them)^{108,109}. This method has similarities to that of semi-structured interviews.

Not strictly following an interview guide, but rather having some topics to discuss in mind, the information shared by the interviewee will be a result of where the conversation 'takes you'¹¹⁰. The spaces in which you walk could also be topics of conversation¹¹¹. In this method it may not be appropriate or 'natural' to get out an interview guide and take notes while walking, because the interviewer will likely take part in an activity (such as mushroom or berry picking, fishing, etc.) or have a more informal conversation along the walk.

Walking interviews are useful for understanding citizens' connection to space and cultural heritage^{112,113}. It adds a spatial component to the interviewing and may be a basis for coastal or marine planning purposes, as it shows how citizens use and experience the areas in question, or potentially what they wish for those areas to be in the future. It is a useful method to use for spatial planning and development, citizen science, ethnographic research, ecosystem service issues connected to space and historical and cultural projects, among others.

5.5.2 Preparations¹¹⁴

- Reflect on what kinds of data you will generate and record.
- If you wish to obtain precise location-based data, remember to bring a GPS device. Reflect on how precise the spatial data needs to be, depending on how important it is in your project/initiative. GPS may be problematic and complex in terms of 'surveillance' and power relations¹¹⁵. Ask participant for permission to register precise GPS location either throughout the interview or at some specific locations.
- If you will be audio recording the interview, bring a recorder. Remember to ask for permission to record/include it in your interview information/consent form according to ethical regulations.
- Prepare a few topics for conversation rather than a bunch of specific questions.
- Decide on whether the interviewees are to decide on the route walked, or whether the interviewer wishes to obtain information on interviewees' various uses of spaces along a set route¹¹⁶. If interviewee is allowed to choose, decide on whether there is any boundary to the area to be walked. Address power dynamics with regards to where interviews take place.
- Prepare recommended equipment: depending on what data you want to obtain; a GPS device could be needed for registering spatial location. Audio recorder may be useful.

¹⁰⁸ Jones & Evans (2012)

¹⁰⁹ Jones et al. (2008)

¹¹⁰ Risvoll (2023). *Personal communication*.

¹¹¹ Evans & Jones (2011)

¹¹² Evans & Jones (2011)

¹¹³ Jones & Evans (2012)

¹¹⁴ Evans & Jones (2011)

¹¹⁵ Proben (2006)

¹¹⁶ Jones et al. (2008)

5.5.3 During

- Take photos along the walk.
- Mark specific spots in the GPS when relevant (if consented by participant).
- If audio recording, mention locations you walk on along the way as another way of mapping the information.

5.5.4 After

- Write down your notes from the interview, preferably immediately post-walk, in order to record information while fresh in memory.
- Give the interviewees the opportunity to read through and confirm the accuracy of the data you have transcribed to be used in your report or initiative
- The amount of information retrieved from the interviewee may vary according to your interviewee and their talkativeness. Getting the information, you are seeking will also depend on how much the interviewee will stick to the topic. It may become necessary to contact the informants for further, more focused, and formal interviews to fill in the gaps after the walking interview.

Example:

- Jones et al. (2008). Exploring Space and Place with Walking Interviews. *Journal of Research Practice*, 4.

5.6 Participatory mapping

Participation level: involve, consult, partnership, potentially empower

Problem type: controllable and uncontrollable

5.6.1 Description

Participatory mapping (not to be confused with the participant mapping you did when planning your citizen engagement project) is an inclusive and collaborative process in which citizens/stakeholders geographically map out information and knowledge about space and the use of spaces, for example in a land-use planning process¹¹⁷, coastal or [Marine spatial planning](#).

In this method, citizens/stakeholders can illustrate their uses of space, and their stories connected to those areas through a map. This can bring up land uses that may typically be ‘forgotten’ when categorizing land use in formal spatial planning processes – the use that cannot be categorized or the activities/ecosystem services that cannot be measured in monetary value but are central to the everyday life or wellbeing of communities¹¹⁸. It can also reveal what areas are accessible and not for different groups, as well as citizens’ perceptions of areas that are not necessarily in ‘use’ by them¹¹⁹. This may be useful for exploring what areas have an associated risk of conflict and can inform decision-

¹¹⁷ Cochrane et al. (2014)

¹¹⁸ Greg and H. Vera Helene (2017)

¹¹⁹ Cochrane et al. (2014)

making in spatial planning process¹²⁰. Participatory mapping can also bring about new and alternative solutions to spatial challenges. It may be used as a tool for co-production of knowledge.

Furthermore, story mapping may be a great tool in a Mission Ocean & Waters initiative that entails historic use and local, cultural knowledge about space¹²¹.

5.6.2 Preparations

Multiple methods exist, some include digital mapping software (GIS platforms), others involve printed maps and markers, stickers, and post-its.

- Decide on which stage in the mapping process citizens are to be involved. What level of engagement are you seeking from them? This may be from the planning stage or it could be only for data collection or confirmation of land use registered in existing maps^{122,123}. Who has decision-making power throughout the process? (see Appendix 1, and Section 2.2/3.3)
- Decide on the format. Is it most appropriate to print out maps for analog mapping or to make a digital platform for participation? A combination? This will likely depend on the scale of the project and the number of citizens expected to be involved, as well as their access to digital platforms and/or distance to the area of interest.
- Consider the spatial resolution of printed maps in case of non-digital mapping workshop. A digital GIS tool generally allows for zooming in and out.
- Find a suitable location for mapping workshop. Attention to accessibility, distance (i.e., *Leave No One Behind*).
- Consider using household sampling as a method of recruitment. Passive recruitment/volunteer sampling may not be representative¹²⁴. Greg et al. (2018) recommends having as many participants as possible to improve representativeness and quantity of data to be analyzed.
- Prepare recommended equipment: Printed maps, post-its, transparent plastic sheets, pens and markers. Technical equipment: ArcGIS or open-source map, eg. QGIS, Geojson.io.

5.6.3 During

- Briefing – introduce the concept of story mapping as well as the topics for discussion/area in question/issues to be explored
- Facilitate the use of maps and info in maps for participants to contextualize their stories/experiences/knowledge

5.6.4 After

- Summarize and digitalize map(s) based on information from the process
- If relevant, write a report on information and knowledge input from the participatory mapping process

¹²⁰ Cochrane et al. (2014)

¹²¹ Cochrane et al. (2014)

¹²² Cochrane et al. (2014)

¹²³ Saija et al. (2017)

¹²⁴ Brown 2017; Greg et al. 2018

- Share maps and/or report with participants for feedback before finalizing and sharing with relevant stakeholders/institutions/policy makers or publishing

Examples:

- CCAT Closure Event (2023). Tools for engaging with local authorities. Coastal Communities Adapting Together. <https://tinyurl.com/vaxkyp84>
- Figueiredo *et al.* (2020). Community and participatory mapping in planning. <https://tinyurl.com/y2a4z4ex>
- Greg *et al.* (2018). “Using public participatory mapping to inform general land use planning and zoning.” *Landscape and Urban Planning* 177: 64-74.
- Greg & Vera Helene (2017). “An empirical analysis of cultural ecosystem values in coastal landscapes.” *Ocean & Coastal Management* 142: 49-60.
- Larzilliere *et al.* (2013). “Interactive scale models, a novel way of prompting constructive participation.” *Bois et Forest des Tropiques*. 67. 21-28.

5.7 Strategic ocean literacy as a way of working

Participation level: involve, consult, partnership, potentially empower

Problem type: controllable and uncontrollable

5.7.1 Description

An ocean literate society is one that ‘understands what the ocean does for us, and what we can do for the ocean’. It has been dubbed as the key enabling factor behind the success of the UN Ocean Decade, that strives to deliver ‘the science we need for the ocean we want’. Recognised as a mechanism for changing society’s relationship with the ocean¹²⁵, and it can also be used as a mechanism to success in your project – speaking to the hearts and minds of your participants through ten dimensions that together are believed to inspire positive action towards looking after our ocean.

Whilst traditional marine education is usually a top-down approach to inform citizens; the evolved concept of ocean literacy is one of bottom-up participation, with a toolbox of methods to collect local knowledge, experiences and co-produce resources. The evolved concept of ocean literacy can therefore be strategically utilised to connect your participants with Mission Ocean & Waters, the goals of your project and the part that different dimensions (Figure 13) can play through their participation. The authors note that this approach must be developed mindful of whether this method is considered ethical in local / project contexts. For example: Are you providing false hope of a positive change with potential of increasing ecoanxiety; or will co-created ocean literacy resources expose vulnerable people or inflame local conflicts.

It is useful to note that the global Ocean Literacy Research Community has developed a bank of freely available questions relating to the dimensions of ocean literacy¹²⁶, which can be adapted for your needs and local contexts. This survey has been undertaken in 12 countries so far at the time of printing for which the data will be made publicly available to inform or frame your projects.

¹²⁵ Glithero et al. (2024)

¹²⁶ McRuer et al. (2025)

More detail on ocean literacy as an example of a way to engage with Mission Ocean & Waters is provided in Section 4.2 ‘Ocean Literacy networks and campaigns as a tool for citizen engagement’.

FIGURE 13. THE 10 DIMENSIONS KNOWN TO AFFECT OCEAN LITERACY.¹²⁷

5.7.2 Preparations

- Ensure the project partners have a common understanding of the evolved concept of ocean literacy and are not considering conventional marine education as an engagement method.
- Consider can your project improve society’s understanding of what the ocean does for it, and what it can do for the ocean?
- Can you nurture this understanding during your participant engagement / dialogues through two-way interactions with participants / collaboration / co-development your project?
- Research the dimensions of ocean literacy¹²⁸. Through careful integration, how can these help to improve the input of knowledge (from participants) or delivery of knowledge to end users.
- Is it ethical to take this approach?¹²⁹
- Do you have the skills and resources to do this effectively?
- Establish clear goals to engaging using this approach, managing expectations with participants from the start.

¹²⁷ McKinley et al. (2023)

¹²⁸ McKinley et al. (2023)

¹²⁹ Morris-Webb et al. (2025 in press)

- Develop specific methods using the guiding questions above, possibly using some of the methods described in the sections above, or utilising guidance from various ocean literacy toolkits and projects^{130 131}.

5.7.3 During

- Develop appropriate and sensitive activities, resources and tools, grounded in ocean literacy / environmental education / behavioural change research.
- Deliver activities and resources using skilled communicators and facilitators.
- Plan two-way dialogues – to capture the information from participants but also provide it back to the community (where appropriate).
- Develop a long-term dissemination plan with participants – how and where would they like to keep / display / disseminate this information?

5.7.4 After

- Evaluate success by considering how did you meet your goals / different dimensions of ocean literacy (Appendix 4102)
- Feedback to participants, ensuring that their contribution is valued and providing them with new ocean literacy resources.

Examples:

- Kelly, R., K. Evans, K. A. Alexander, S. Bettiol, S. Corney, C. Cullen-Knox, C. Cvitanovic, K. de Salas, G. R. Emad, L. Fullbrook, C. Garcia, S. Ison, S. D. Ling, C. Macleod, A. Meyer, L. Murray, M. Murunga, K. Nash, K. Norris, M. Oellermann, J. Scott, J. Stark, G. Wood & G. T. Pecl. (2022). *"Connecting to the oceans: Supporting ocean literacy and public engagement."* Reviews in Fish Biology and Fisheries / <https://futureseas2030.org/>
- McRuer, J., Glithero, D., McKinley, E., Pagès, J., Fauville, G., Morris-Webb, E., Hart, N., Strang, C., Christofolletti, R., Hulme, S., Grainger, E., Pinheiro, B., Payne, D., Bridge, N., Lindoso, V., Machado Martins, I., Zandvliet, D., Bueno Fernandes, M., Bumbeer, J., & Shellock, R. (2025). Co-designing the Ocean & Society Survey—A Global Tool for Understanding People-Ocean Connections and Mobilizing Ocean Action. Ocean & Society.
- Morris-Webb, E. Kindlon, D & Borklund, C. (2025 *in prep*). Strategic ocean literacy: Ensuring European project activities meaningfully align with both their ambitions and the evolved concept of ocean literacy. In "Handbook of Inclusive Methodologies: How methods and methodologies contribute to inclusive and equitable coastal transition", Edited by M. Gustavsson, S. Solnør and K. Rønningen. EmpowerUs Project.

¹³⁰Kelly et al. (2022)

¹³¹ Santoro et al. (2017)

6 Recommendations for Enhancing Citizen Engagement with Mission Ocean & Waters

Based on the synthesis of theory, practical tools, and project experiences presented in this toolbox, we propose the following eight key recommendations for aiming to strengthen citizen engagement in support of the Mission:

- 1. Tailor Engagement to Problem Type**
Use the diagnostic tools provided (Figure 2 / Figure 7) to align engagement strategies with the level of complexity, risk, and ambiguity in the problem you are addressing. Prioritise inclusive and empowering approaches for uncontrollable, wicked problems.
- 2. Plan Strategically from the Start**
Use the guiding questions (Table 1 / Table 7) early in your project development to clarify objectives, stakeholders, ethical considerations, and methods for evaluating engagement impact.
- 3. Embed Equity and Inclusion: Who, why, how**
Apply the *Leave No One Behind* (LNOB) principle systematically—identify who is being excluded, why, and design participation methods to overcome barriers.
- 4. Integrate Evaluation into Project Design**
Select and adapt evaluation tools (Table 10, 11, 12) at the outset. Track both outcomes and processes and adjust as needed during implementation.
- 5. Support Deliberative Participation**
Foster meaningful participation by supporting structured, well-facilitated processes (see list of tools in Part 5)
- 6. Promote Knowledge Co-Production**
Encourage collaboration between citizens, stakeholders and scientists. Recognize and value different types of knowledge—practical, experiential, and scientific.
- 7. Work Towards Policy Influence**
Aim to ensure that citizen engagement outputs are positioned to inform decision-making at local, national, and EU levels. This includes sharing outcomes with relevant bodies and contributing to Mission-wide learning. The tools provided in Section 2.4 / 3.5 and Appendix 4 can help you to consider this.
- 8. Share and Reuse Tools and Learnings**
Contribute to [WaveLinks](#) and other open platforms by sharing templates, tools, and examples from your work. Find the repository most appropriate for your work to be available in the long term. Adapt this toolbox for your context and help improve future versions.

By applying these recommendations, we can collectively strengthen the legitimacy, effectiveness, and reach of citizen participation in marine and freshwater governance and help achieve the goals of the Mission: Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030.

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Additional sources – Policy reports, briefings, web resources, and grey literature

- The Bertelsmann Foundation June 2022: Next level citizen participation in the EU Institutionalising European Citizens’ Assemblies. Authors: Gabriele Abels, Alberto Alemanno, Ben Crum, Andrey Demidov, Dominik Hierlemann, Anna Renkamp, Alexander Trechsel.
- KNOCA Briefing no. 11 2024 November: Developments in Sub-National Climate Assemblies Lessons from Local and Regional Levels Carolin Brodtmann and Ines Omann
- KNOCA Briefing No.10 2024 July: Towards Permanent Climate Citizens’ Assemblies: Learning from the Early Adopters. Nabila Abbas and Graham Smith
- Risvoll, C. (2023). *Personal communication*.

Webpages:

- EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/restore-our-ocean-and-waters_en
- Implementation Plans for the EU Missions. https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/knowledge-publications-tools-and-data/publications/all-publications/implementation-plans-eu-missions_en
- International association for public participation. (2014). IAP2’s Public participation spectrum. https://iap2.org.au/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/IAP2_Public_Participation_Spectrum.pdf
- The Norwegian Reference Fleet: <https://www.hi.no/en/hi/cruises-and-field-work/the-reference-fleet>
- Webpage with a number of tools: <http://actioncatalogue.eu/search>
- EU project with toolbox: <http://gap2.eu/methodological-toolbox/>
- Manual to guide public participation in central government: <https://involve.org.uk/sites/default/files/uploads/Making-a-Difference-.pdf>
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- <https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/474dbf1a1f8f491199ad0489877153b9>

- EmpowerUs project: <https://empowerus-project.eu/>
- PREP4BLUE call for Pilot Action Awards (engaging citizens in Mission Ocean & Waters):
<https://prep4blue.eu/prep4blue-pilot-activity-funding-engaging-citizens-in-mission-ocean/>

Appendix 1: Additional planning templates to guide project planning

TABLE 19. GUIDING QUESTIONS FOR STAKEHOLDER MAPPING.

What is the purpose of including citizens/stakeholders in my project?	Focus on antecedents
Do they represent a knowledge position?	Yes/No
Will citizens/stakeholders be affected by activities/the initiative/the project outcomes?	Yes/No
Is citizen/stakeholder involvement necessary for goal obtainment because of their power position?	Yes/No
Is citizen/stakeholder involvement necessary for goal obtainment of legitimations reasons?	Yes/No
Is citizen/stakeholder involvement necessary because they represent means that contribute to solutions?	Yes/No
Who defines the rules in relation to the given issue?	
May some citizens/stakeholders obstruct the activity to be implemented?	Yes/No
What is the citizens/stakeholder authority in terms of allocating rewards, recognition and sanctions?	
Will some groups of citizens/stakeholders experience disadvantage if excluded from the engagement?	Yes/No
Who can represent 'the voiceless'?	
Guiding questions: Power	Comments
Which relationships exist between the selected citizen/stakeholders?	Alliances
What is the actor's authority in terms of setting objectives and norms?	
What is the actor's authority in terms of allocating or denying resources to other actors?	
What is the actor's authority in terms of defining others' tasks and responsibilities?	
What is the actor's authority in terms of controlling access to knowledge/information?	
What is the actor's authority in terms of allocating rewards, recognition and sanctions?	
What is the actor's authority in terms of structuring the participation in decision-making processes?	
Guiding questions: Legitimations	Comments
To what degree is the actor's influence acquired through institutional position?	

To what degree is the actor's formal influence acquired by law and regulations?	
To what degree is the actor's Influence acquired through media/social media	
To what degree are the actor's interests coherent or conflictive with other actors' interests?	
What potential benefits and risks arise for her / him if the issue is addressed/the problem is solved?	
What prior experience does the actor have on the problem/issue to be addressed?	
Guiding questions: Resources	Comments
Material and nonmaterial resources different actors possess or have control over: Knowledge, expertise, skills effectively address the issue/solve the problem?	
Material and nonmaterial resources different actors possess or have control over: arises from learned skills and experience and is expressed in the ability to solve practical problems	
Material and nonmaterial resources different actors possess or have control over: technology, effectively address the issue/solve the problem?	
Material and nonmaterial resources different actors possess or have control over economy effectively address the issue/solve the problem?	
Resources from communication and negotiating skills to grasp the crux of the issue and to communicate clearly and concisely, conveying a coherent message, persuading others and thereby asserting one's own interests.	
What options exist to increase the actor's interest and engagement, or to dismantle obstacles?	
What resources relate to social categories of age?	
What resources relate to social categories of gender?	

Appendix 2: Additional tools to help planning evaluation and monitoring

TABLE 20. GUIDING REFLECTION QUESTIONS FOR STEP 3 – MONITORING AND ASSESSING CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT, TO SUPPORT THE PROCESS OF STARTING TO CONSIDER WHAT TO EVALUATE¹³²

Step 3: Monitoring and assessing citizen engagement	Questions before and during start of project	Comments
	What type of participation is our aim?	Before start of project. Reflect on Table 1 / Table 7 For evaluating, see Table 10, Table 11, Table 12
	What depth of participation do we want?	Before start of the project. Related to the level or responsibility
	How can we pinpoint exactly type and level of participation?	Before project start – several examples below
	Are the methods selected appropriate?	After project start – make changes if necessary
	What is working well/not working well and why?	During project. For each citizen/stakeholder engagement activity, make detailed minutes that describes the process.
	What is the actual impact of the process on the results?	During project and after the project end
	What is the actual impact of the process on the participants? (do they feel empowered?)	During project and after the project end
	Questions to evaluate outcome of your initiative	Comments
	Did we meet our aims and objectives?	Refer to your answers in Table
	Questions to evaluate the process of your initiative	Comments
	Were the methods selected appropriate?	During project and after the project end
	What worked well and why?	During project and after the project end
	What did not work well and why?	During project and after the project end
	What are the lessons learned?	After the project end. To inform the general debate on Missions and participatory processes
	Questions to include participants perspectives	Comment
	Did we meet their aims and expectations?	You can use different types of tools to gather this information e.g., e-mail, survey or workshop.
	What are the participants' views on the outcome, process and impact?	You can use different types of tools to gather this information e.g., e-mail, survey or workshop.

¹³² Inspired by Durham E., Baker H., Smith M., Moore E. & Morgan V. (2014). The BiodivERsA Stakeholder Engagement Handbook. BiodivERsA, Paris (108 pp).

Appendix 3: Examples to illustrate steps of participation

Reflecting on what we have learned about the steps of participation (see Figure X below), we can identify that traditionally many scientific projects may have tackled controlled, low risk problems, and then informed citizens about the knowledge they have revealed, in a one-way attempt to keep scientists informed. However, more and more transdisciplinary projects aim to solve more uncontrollable problems, with uncertain risks, by consulting, involving and/or collaborating with specific experts and knowledge holders, for instance in participatory science for fisheries management. As citizen science reaches has peaked the interests of governments and scientists alike, as a way of both collecting information and involving society with more uncontrollable and ambiguous problems, we have the potential to empower citizens in their decision-making potential, if done well. Below are some more specific examples of how the steps could be applied to specific problems through projects that engage citizens in The Mission.

FIGURE 14. DIAGNOSTIC TOOL FOR PARTICIPATION LEVEL. VISUALISING THE STEPS OF PARTICIPANT ENGAGEMENT FROM INFORMING TO EMPOWERING, ACCORDING TO SCOPE OF RISKS AND EXPECTATIONS WITHIN PROJECTS.

Controllable problem: blue mussel toxins

We will start at the far left of Figure 14 with an example of a controllable problem, which means that there is little conflict regarding the issue at hand and the scope of risk is simple. Take the issue of food safety, like the toxin levels in blue mussels. Arguably, most people agree that they want to be able to eat mussels without toxins, and the science in this matter is settled (the level of toxins safe for human consumption for instance). Moving along the orange arrow, this is categorized as a controllable problem. Next, move up the figure to check the type of input needed. It can be assumed that scientists are relevant actors involved in knowledge production for the advice of toxins in blue mussels. Looking at the levels of citizen participation, it is reasonable to assume that it suffices to inform citizens about the toxin levels. Summing up, if you have a controllable problem with little risk and a general consensus (for example, what toxin levels in blue mussels are safe), one can assume that this is a a) controllable problem with simple risk; b) the type of input needed is knowledge from scientists as relevant actors; and this means that informing citizens is a sufficient step of participation.

Uncontrollable problem: coastal erosion due to sea level rise

Moving right of Figure 14 above, on the continuum of the orange arrow towards uncontrollable problems, the complexity increases when looking up towards the scope of risk (complex, uncertain and ambiguous risk), the type of input and who the relevant actors are. Knowledge input is not enough for these problems; you will also need experience and reflections and potentially even co-production and co-responsibility from a broader set of stakeholders, including citizens.

Take the example of a coastal community where coastal erosion is threatening the safety of those living there, as the beaches are eroding. So, you know this is an uncontrollable problem, but what is the scope of risk (moving up the figure), and consequently, the type of input needed? If the scope of risk is ambiguous, the figure suggests co-production and -responsibility, involving scientists, practice experts, stakeholders and civil society. What step of participation is required - involvement, collaboration or even empowerment? What actors are relevant to include in the process?

In this example, we suggest the following: Knowledge input from science, but also from practice experts such as people with experience-based knowledge about, for example, how this case compares to other coastal areas or how coastal erosion has developed over time. In addition, stakeholders such as house owners should be included in the decision-making process: What type of actions do they prefer as this impacts them directly? For example, would they prefer to be reallocated? Would they prefer to build a concrete barrier protecting their house? Also, civil society should be included in the process, since this will impact them in different ways, for example, access to the coast or economic cost of the process. Importantly, all of these actors are also civil society, including scientists.

Appendix 4: Mapping your pathway to impact: Towards Mission Ocean & Waters' citizen participation targets and societal ocean literacy.

Often, working backwards from your goals (what you want to achieve) will help a project attain its goals. Below are some tools to help you do think about what you are trying to achieve, in terms of Mission Ocean & Waters, and the wider impact that you hope to have on improving people's understanding of what the ocean does for them, and what they can do for the ocean (ocean literacy). These tools may help you to plan or evaluate your project but also may help to visualise your pathway to impact in your funding applications.

FIGURE 15. EXAMPLE OF A MISSION OCEAN & WATERS CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT IMPACT MAPPER ¹³³

¹³³ Mission Ocean Implementation Plan

Aims and impact of ocean literacy within project: mapping template

Direct target audience (who will you deliver this to directly?)	Your citizen engagement activities / outputs:	Dimensions of Ocean Literacy	Principles of Ocean Science	Evaluation metric?	Will result be paid forward to other audiences? Will you evaluate this?
		<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Communi- -cation</p> <p>Activism</p> <p>Knowled ge</p> <p>Awarene ss</p> <p>Attitudes</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Behaviou</p> <p>Emocean</p> <p>Access & Experien</p> <p>Adaptive Capacity</p> <p>Trust & Transpar ency</p> </div> </div>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Earth has one big ocean with many features. 1. The ocean & life in the ocean shape the features of Earth. 1. The ocean is a major influence on weather & climate. 1. The ocean makes Earth habitable. 1. The ocean supports a great diversity of life and ecosystems. 1. The ocean and humans are inextricably interconnected. 1. The ocean is largely unexplored. 		
		<p>☆ Very slight incidental / side-focus</p> <p>★ Very slight incidental / side-focus</p> <p>★ A target focus</p> <p>★ A strong target focus</p> <p>★ The main focus of the project / very strong focus</p>			

FIGURE 16. PLANNING TOOL TO MAP STRATEGIC IMPACT ON DIMENSIONS OF OCEAN LITERACY: AND HOW YOU WILL DEVELOP AND EVALUATE THIS.